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Summary

This comparative analysis of agricultural, economic, and biodiversity policies in Cameroon, Kenya, and Colombia explores nature and equity in contexts of agricultural expansion. Three complementary methods were used: a discourse analysis of policy documents and government plans using the Nature Futures Framework and the Life Frames Framework; an evaluation of budget allocated to implement major agricultural and biodiversity conservation policies and interviews with stakeholders to understand the challenges and opportunities at the nexus of biodiversity conservation, food production, and economic development.

The results reveal a shared struggle to harmonize agricultural development with biodiversity conservation, despite distinct institutional capacities, historical pathways, and sociocultural contexts. While in all three countries there is increasing recognition of how vital biodiversity is for national development, agriculture continues to dominate policy agendas and resource allocation. This imbalance creates structural barriers that limit progress toward genuinely transformative socio-ecological governance.

In all countries, nature is primarily framed in instrumental terms. Policies in Kenya and Cameroon emphasize biodiversity as a means to enhance productivity, climate resilience, and rural livelihoods. Colombia shows an even stronger utilitarian orientation, treating nature largely as an external resource for economic growth under “Nature for Society” paradigms. Although ecological stewardship is acknowledged in national strategies, intrinsic and relational values—especially those rooted in Indigenous cosmologies—remain weakly expressed in implementation. The near absence of “living as” framings indicates that alternative ontologies have yet to meaningfully shape policy design or land-use governance. A central constraint is the persistent mismatch between stated ambitions and financial commitments. Biodiversity-related ministries in all three countries receive minimal funding compared with agriculture, reinforcing a development logic that privileges short-term productivity over long-term ecological resilience. Kenya’s environmental budget seldom surpasses 0.3 percent of national expenditure; Cameroon displays similar disparities; and Colombia’s resource allocations continue to favour agricultural expansion. Institutional fragmentation further undermines integrated governance. In Cameroon and Kenya, agricultural and environmental institutions operate largely in silos, coordinating mainly in response to crises such as deforestation or encroachment. In Colombia, fragmentation reflects deeper epistemic divides rooted in colonial-modernity imaginaries that separate humans from nature, marginalizing Indigenous relational worldviews and limiting cohesive strategies for landscape management. Community participation and knowledge integration remain limited. Kenya’s community forests and conservancies operate unevenly and often lack sustained funding. In Cameroon, rural populations demonstrate limited awareness of policy frameworks and encounter weak enforcement capacities. Colombia’s governance frameworks insufficiently incorporate Indigenous histories and ontologies, risking conflict and exclusion. Across all three countries, inadequate mechanisms for participation and benefit-sharing undermine legitimacy and reduce policy effectiveness.

Despite these common constraints, divergent trajectories emerge. In Kenya there is growing momentum for restoration-oriented initiatives such as the National Tree Planting Initiative. Cameroon’s recent strategies reflect more holistic approaches, accompanied by grassroots interest in agroecology and nature-based solutions. Colombia’s scholarly and policy discourse exposes deeper structural tensions, suggesting that transformative change will require shifts not only in policy but also in national imaginaries and governance logics.

1. Introduction

As globalization continues to accelerate, the rising demand for commodities in biodiversity-rich countries of the Global South has opened substantial market opportunities. At the same time, this surge in global trade has intensified ecological pressures, resulting in significant threats to biodiversity (IPBES, 2019; Lenzen et al., 2012; UNEP, 2021). Studies in Central and East Africa reveal that export-oriented agriculture can drive forest conversion and habitat loss, while smallholder systems struggle to compete or transition to sustainable practices (Achieng et al., 2023; Ingram et al. 2025, Ryan et al., 2014). In Kenya, evidence from the tea and horticulture sectors shows how intensification can simultaneously generate rural incomes and erode natural capital if not carefully managed (Mutoko et al., 2014; Nyangena et al., 2020). Countries like Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya illustrate this phenomenon well: while they are deeply integrated into international markets through food exports, they also serve as vital biodiversity hotspots.

Conserving biodiversity is essential in confronting the ongoing sixth mass extinction and in safeguarding the ecosystem services fundamental to human well-being. Yet, the large-scale agricultural production needed to satisfy both domestic and international demands frequently results in unsustainable practices that undermine the restoration and maintenance of natural ecosystems. This tension highlights the importance of investigating how agricultural production, biodiversity conservation, and economic development intersect in these contexts.

This study focuses on Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya as case studies and the three main countries in TC4BE project to examine the intricate interrelationships between agricultural expansion, biodiversity conservation, and human well-being, particularly among rural production communities.

General objective

To understand the complex interdependencies between agricultural production and biodiversity conservation in the context of large-scale agricultural expansion aimed at meeting domestic and international food demands.

Specific objectives

- Identify and map the main biodiversity, agricultural, and economic policies associated with telecoupled agrifood systems that have influenced land use and biodiversity conservation between 2010 and 2020.
- Analyze the principal agricultural and biodiversity conservation policies through the lens of emerging frameworks related to nature futures.

The study applies three complementary methods:

- A. Discourse analysis of key policy documents and government plans from each administration during the study period, using the Nature Futures Framework and the Life Frames Framework;
- B. Evaluation of financial allocations for the implementation of major agricultural and biodiversity conservation policies.
- C. Collection of insights from interviews with key stakeholders to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities at the nexus of biodiversity conservation, food production, and economic development.

2. Methodology

2.1 Discourse Analysis

The objective of analysing how different values of nature are represented in key policy documents is operationalised using the Nature Futures Framework (NFF) and the Life Frames Framework (LFF).

2.1.1 Nature Futures Framework

The Nature Futures Framework (NFF) is a heuristic tool designed to illuminate the diverse and positive interactions between humans and nature (Lundquist et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2020). In contrast to conventional global environmental assessments that mainly emphasize human impacts on the environment, the NFF shifts the focus to how nature contributes to human well-being and drives sustainable development (Paz Duran et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2020). The framework outlines three primary value-based perspectives through which people relate to and appreciate nature:

- "Nature for nature" underscores the intrinsic value of nature and the importance of maintaining its ecological functions.
- "Nature for society" highlights the utilitarian benefits nature offers for human needs and purposes.
- "Nature as culture" views humans as inseparable from nature, emphasizing co-evolution and shared existence.

These perspectives are represented within a triangular diagram, with each vertex corresponding to one of the core value orientations. The interior of the triangle represents hybrid or integrated value positions that combine elements of the three perspectives (Figure 1). Due to its ability to accommodate a wide range of human–nature relationships, the NFF is employed in this study as a framework for analysing policies related to agriculture and biodiversity conservation.

Figure 1 The Nature Futures Framework (NFF) and the three main value perspectives constituting the relative space within the NFF

Paz Duran et al. (2023).. [https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/535608/1/s11625-023-01316-1%20\(2\).pdf](https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/535608/1/s11625-023-01316-1%20(2).pdf)

In order to systematically assess the nature-related values emphasized in public policies and the types of human–nature relationships they promote, Table 1 is used to operationalise the NFF. This approach seeks to identify the specific values embedded in policies related to or affecting nature and assign relevant references to the corresponding categories. As the value dimensions within the Nature Futures Framework (NFF) are not mutually exclusive, this framework is designed to both distinguish these perspectives and demonstrate their interconnectedness (Paz Duran et al., 2023).

Table 1 Nature Futures Framework guide for policy analysis

Policy	Year	Policy description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
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2.1.2 Life Futures Framework

An inclusive typology of the diverse ways people value nature, the Life Frames Framework (LFF) was developed through the IPBES Values Assessment (2023). This framework reveals how individuals, institutions, and policy frameworks prioritize particular nature-related values based on their underlying conceptualizations of the human–nature relationship. Each "life frame" embodies a unique perspective on nature, influencing the kinds of values that guide decisions and actions.

The 'living from' frame emphasizes instrumental values, focusing on nature's role in providing material benefits such as food, timber, or income from activities like ecotourism. The 'living in' frame reflects relational values, portraying nature as integral to daily life, cultural identity, and well-being, both mental and physical. The 'living with' frame incorporates both intrinsic and relational values, recognizing the significance of ecological systems that sustain life and extending moral concern to non-human beings, including the acknowledgment of their inherent right to exist. Finally, the 'living as' frame embodies a deep sense of unity and interconnectedness with nature. Rooted in spiritual or Indigenous worldviews, this perspective sees humans as part of a sacred, living network that includes ancestors and other-than-human entities.

Compared to the Nature Futures Framework (NFF), the LFF offers a lens that is broader in scope and more detailed in specificity for understanding the diversity of values attributed to nature, especially by explicitly incorporating the often-overlooked 'living as' perspective. Given this broader scope, a similar analytical method to that used with the NFF is proposed to identify the values emphasized in public policy and to evaluate the types of relationships with nature those policies encourage.

To facilitate this analysis, Table 2 is presented to categorize policy content according to the four life frames, enabling researchers to identify which values are most prominently reflected in biodiversity-related policies and to document supporting references or excerpts accordingly.

Table 2 Life Frames Framework Guide for policy analysis

Policy	Year	Policy description	'living from' frame centres on nature's capacity to provide tangible resources that support livelihoods.	The 'living in' frame recognizes nature as an essential part of people's daily lives, identities, and cultural practices.	'living with' frame acknowledges the importance of life-supporting ecological systems and moral consideration for other-than-human beings.	'living as' frame expresses a profound sense of oneness, kinship, and interdependence with nature.
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2.2 Desk-based study of Government Investments that incentivize agricultural production and biodiversity conservation

A desk-based analysis was conducted to assess government investments in agricultural production, land use and biodiversity conservation. The main goal was to determine which public policies attracted the most attention and funding over time, based on the premise that budget allocations reflect policy priorities. By examining the distribution of public funds across various policies, the study aimed to identify the areas that received the greatest emphasis. This budget-oriented approach also enabled a comparison of policy importance and helped trace shifts in priorities over time.

To carry out the analysis, the study systematically reviewed policy documents and budgetary records from agricultural and environmental sectors in each country. It sought to identify the policies enacted during the study period and assess the financial resources dedicated to each. To focus on the most impactful policies, the 80/20 Pareto principle was applied. This principle posits that a small proportion of inputs (policies) typically accounts for the majority of outcomes (investments). Using this framework, the analysis highlighted the top 20% of policies that received roughly 80% of total public investment in these sectors. This filtering process allowed the study to zero in on the most financially significant initiatives.

From this filtered subset, we conducted a deeper analysis to identify patterns in national policy implementation. The analysis looked at two key dimensions: the frequency with which each policy appeared in the national budget and the total amount of funding it received over the entire study period. This dual metric approach, tracking both consistency and financial magnitude, provided insights into not just which policies were heavily funded but also which were sustained over time.

This two-pronged analysis revealed important trends. Policies that appeared regularly in the budget and received substantial, consistent funding were identified as the government's core and enduring priorities. Conversely, policies that received large sums in only a few years, or were funded intermittently were considered less integral to long-term strategic planning. In sum, this study offers a comprehensive overview of how governments have balanced objectives for agricultural productivity and biodiversity conservation through their investment choices.

2.3 Stakeholder interviews

The objective was to collect qualitative insights on national and sectoral policies affecting biodiversity and land use, and explore potential transformations needed to protect biodiversity in the increasing demand for commodities.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to investigate policies affecting biodiversity and land use and explore potential transformations needed to protect biodiversity in the increasing demand for commodities. These interviews targeted key stakeholders chosen to represent diverse perspectives on public policies related to agriculture and biodiversity, ensuring a balanced and comprehensive understanding of the policies. Participants were selected from two main groups: government officials responsible for agricultural and biodiversity-related policies, and non-government stakeholders, such as researchers and experts in biodiversity and land use, who could provide critical and independent perspectives. This dual approach ensured the inclusion of both policy implementers and external observers, enabling a broader and more nuanced examination of policy formulation, implementation, and impact.

The semi-structured format of the interviews allowed for in-depth discussions while maintaining consistency across participants. An interview guide was designed to focus on identifying key public policy instruments that have influenced biodiversity and land use over the past 15 years. Stakeholders were asked to elaborate on the objectives of these policies, their perceived effects on biodiversity and land use, and to reflect on what could have been done differently if they were

involved in the design or implementation of these policies. Additionally, the interviews sought to capture stakeholders' perspectives on the transformations required to safeguard biodiversity in light of increasing global demand for commodities. Thus, the core questions guiding the interviews were: Which environmental and agricultural policies do you consider the most significant in the past 15 years? What impact have they had? How do you envision the country's future, and what changes would you make to these policies to achieve that vision?

Content analysis was employed to identify recurring themes and patterns in the responses. For instance, actors identified specific periods of change and continuity between policy goals and mechanisms to achieve those goals. The analysis paid particular attention to areas of convergence and divergence between government and non-government stakeholders, the perceived successes and shortcomings of existing or previous policies, and specific recommendations for future policy design and implementation. The insights derived from these interviews provide a detailed understanding of how sectoral policies have shaped biodiversity conservation and land use over time. Furthermore, they offer valuable recommendations for future policies that aim to balance the need for increased commodity production with the critical goal of protecting biodiversity.

3. Results

3.1 Cameroon

Cameroon's national policy landscape reflects a growing awareness of the need to balance biodiversity conservation with agricultural production, particularly in the face of increasing demographic pressure, economic development goals, and climate change. Several key policy documents issued by the national government outline strategic directions aimed at achieving this balance while promoting sustainable development and poverty reduction.

One of the foundational policy frameworks is the **Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP) 2010–2019**, which sought to drive economic growth and job creation, with agriculture positioned as a key sector for poverty alleviation. While biodiversity conservation was not a central focus, the GESP acknowledged the importance of environmental sustainability in achieving long-term development. This emphasis was strengthened in its successor, the **National Development Strategy 2020–2030 (NDS30)**, which integrates environmental protection more explicitly, including targets related to land management, forest preservation, and the sustainable use of natural resources. The NDS30 represents a shift towards more integrated planning, with biodiversity conservation framed as a cross-cutting issue relevant to various sectors including agriculture, infrastructure, and mining.

Cameroon's Vision 2035 serves as the overarching long-term policy goal, aiming to transform the country into an emerging economy. Within this vision, sustainable environmental management, including biodiversity conservation, is recognized as essential for inclusive and resilient growth. This vision is operationalized through sectoral strategies such as the **National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP II)**, which provides a roadmap for the protection and sustainable use of biodiversity. Aligned with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), NBSAP II emphasizes mainstreaming biodiversity into national policies, promoting community-based conservation, and strengthening governance mechanisms.

In parallel, Cameroon's **Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) 2021** and the **National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (2015–2019)** underscore the interconnectedness between climate resilience, agriculture, and biodiversity. These documents highlight sustainable land use and climate-smart agriculture as critical strategies for mitigating climate change impacts while preserving ecosystems. They call for the protection of forest cover, the adoption of agroecological practices, and the reinforcement of institutional capacities to manage environmental risks.

The **National Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Assessment (NBESA) 2022**, conducted by the Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection, and Sustainable Development (MINEPDED), provides a

scientific basis for decision-making. It emphasizes the value of ecosystem services for livelihoods, especially in rural areas dependent on agriculture, and identifies threats such as habitat loss and unsustainable farming practices. The report recommends nature-based solutions and improved policy coordination between agriculture and environmental sectors.

Complementing these efforts, the **State of Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture policy report (2015)** by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER) and the **BIOFIN Initiative (2025)** hosted by MINEPDED highlight the role of agrobiodiversity in ensuring food security and resilience. It calls for conservation of local crop varieties, sustainable agricultural intensification, and the integration of biodiversity into agricultural extension services.

Biodiversity restoration is central to Cameroon's forest policy. However, it is not mentioned in the Horizon 2020 strategy (Office of the Prime Minister, 2014). In contrast, the expansionist national cocoa policy and farmers indicated few practices of forest protection, whilst recognising that forest loss and degradation had occurred, this was not attributed to their farming practices. Forests can be seen mainly from a utilitarian *Nature for Society* perspective, for its role in water provision, soil fertility and climate regulation. Whilst state policies to protect forests and biodiversity are enshrined in policy and laws, governed by MINFOF, ANAFOR and MINEPDED, customary governance exists in vary degrees of intensity and also offers a level of forest protection (nature for nature) as well as also a way to exploit biodiversity (i.e. nature for society), for example harvesting timber and non-timber forests products including bush meat.

Cameroon's 2011 **Support Program for the Improvement of Agricultural Productivity, National Indicative Program 2014-2020**, and the 2014 **Horizon 2020 Recovery and Development Plan for Cocoa and Coffee Value Chains** aim to double national production to 600,000 tons of cocoa annually by 2020 (Office of the Prime Minister, 2014). This objective was not achieved and was postponed to 2030. Sustainability and sustainable cocoa is mentioned but not defined in the Horizon 2020 strategy (Office of the Prime Minister, 2014). The Horizon 2020 does not mention cocoa as driver of deforestation or biodiversity loss, nor does discuss its relationship to forests

Together, these national-level strategies reflect Cameroon's commitment to promoting agricultural development with attention to sustainable development, and increasing awareness of biodiversity conservation.

3.1.1 Discourse analysis

3.1.1.1 Nature Futures Framework

By examining key policy documents of Cameroon such as the Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP) 2010–2019, the National Development Strategy 2020–2030 (NDS30), Vision 2035, the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan II (NBSAP II), the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) 2021, the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC) 2015–2019, the National Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Assessment (NBESA) 2022, and the State of Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture policy report (2015), this analysis aims to explore how Cameroon's policies reflect and promote the NFF perspectives, and identify areas for strengthening policy coherence and implementation.

The *Nature for Nature* perspective emphasizes the intrinsic value of biodiversity and the necessity of preserving ecosystems for their own sake. Cameroon's NBSAP II embodies this approach by setting targets to increase forest cover and promote sustainable forest management. The strategy outlines actions such as reforestation programs, community-based conservation, and the use of alternative energy sources to reduce pressure on forests. Additionally, the NBESA 2022 highlights the country's exceptional biodiversity and the need for spatial planning to conserve ecosystems and enhance resilience. Despite these commitments, challenges remain in achieving the desired outcomes. The GESP 2010–2019, while focusing on economic growth and poverty reduction, did not

sufficiently integrate biodiversity conservation, leading to potential conflicts between development and environmental goals. The NDS30 addresses this gap by incorporating environmental considerations into its framework, aiming for sustainable development through structural transformation and increased agricultural productivity.

The *Nature for Society* perspective underscores the role of biodiversity in supporting human well-being, particularly through ecosystem services such as food, water, and climate regulation. Cameroon's Vision 2035 acknowledges the importance of sustainable agriculture and forestry in reducing rural poverty and enhancing food security. The strategy advocates for agricultural intensification, improved land management, and the development of agro-pastoral systems to increase productivity and resilience. The PNACC 2015–2019 further reinforces this perspective by proposing adaptation measures across various sectors, including agriculture, to reduce vulnerability to climate change. The NDCs 2021 also emphasizes the role of sustainable land management and climate-smart agriculture in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing food security. However, the implementation of these strategies faces obstacles such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and insufficient capacity at local levels. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts across sectors and levels of governance to ensure that biodiversity conservation translates into tangible benefits for communities.

The *Nature as Culture* perspective highlights the cultural and spiritual significance of biodiversity, recognizing the deep connections between communities and their natural environments. Cameroon's NBSAP II emphasizes the inclusion of gender and vulnerable groups in biodiversity management, advocating for collaborative approaches that respect traditional knowledge and practices. The NBESA 2022 also notes the importance of integrating indigenous and local knowledge into ecosystem management to enhance effectiveness and equity. Moreover, the State of Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture report (2015) underscores the need to preserve agrobiodiversity and traditional farming systems that contribute to food security and cultural identity. Despite these acknowledgments, the practical integration of cultural values into biodiversity governance remains limited. Strengthening the participation of local communities in decision-making processes and recognizing the value of traditional knowledge are essential steps toward achieving more inclusive and culturally sensitive biodiversity policies.

Figure 1 Visual representation of the NFF and Cameroon's national policies embodied in policy documents

Figure 1 presents a systemic diagram based on the Nature Futures Framework (NFF), a triangular model that categorizes policy orientations according to three core value perspectives through which people relate to nature. The apexes of the triangle represent "Nature for Nature" (top): prioritizing nature's intrinsic value and ecological integrity; "Nature for Society" (bottom-left): emphasizing nature's utility in supporting human needs, such as food, jobs, and economic growth; and "Nature as Culture" (bottom-right): highlighting relational and cultural connections where humans are seen as part of nature. Cameroon's key national policies have been plotted within this triangle based on the values they emphasize: In the "Nature for Nature" corner, three policies, Cameroon's NDCs (2021), the National Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Assessment (NBESA, 2022), and the REDD+ Strategy (2018), strongly emphasize conservation and environmental protection. These policies reflect a preservationist ethos, prioritizing biodiversity and ecosystem health as ends in themselves. In contrast, the "Nature for Society" corner is the most populated, hosting foundational development documents such as Cameroon Vision 2035, NDS 2020–2030, GESP 2010–2019, and key sectoral reports like the FODECC Annual Report (2021) and the Cocoa & Coffee Plan (2014). These prioritize productivity, rural livelihoods, and economic transformation, treating nature primarily as a means to improve human welfare. The "Nature as Culture" corner, though less populated, includes the Green Cocoa Landscape Program (2020), which integrates cultural landscapes and participatory, place-based approaches to sustainable cocoa farming. This placement reflects the program's acknowledgment of local communities' roles in managing and coexisting with nature. This program can be considered as a "trial" of an integrated landscape approach, that was extended and changed during its implementation to focus on both bottom up landscape level initiatives and especially collaboration among landscape level stakeholders, and in parallel ensure the national level embeddedness and multiple national sectoral government commitment. Whilst it is not the first long term landscape program, there are few other long term projects which integrate landscape and national level actions, notably GIZ's Programme for Sustainable Management of Natural Resources in the South West Province of Cameroon (PSMNR). Landscape programmes and policies bridging scales and addressing high biodiversity, telecoupled

landscapes have not been replicated recently, due to the costs and coordination efforts, as well as uncertainties of their longer term outcomes (Ingram et al., 2025),.

Several policies span multiple values and are placed between corners. The Deforestation-free Cocoa Roadmap (2021) bridges Nature for Society and Nature as Culture, suggesting a shift toward sustainable supply chains grounded in community involvement. The MINADER Biodiversity Report (2015), situated between Nature for Nature and Nature for Society, emphasizes both biodiversity preservation and agricultural benefits. The PRSP (2003) is tentatively positioned between Nature for Nature and Nature as Culture, depending on interpretive emphasis on environmental sustainability and cultural embeddedness. Figure 3 therefore visualizes the balance and tensions among conservation, development, and cultural integration in Cameroon's policy landscape, offering insights into how public policies frame human–nature relationships.

The Cameroonian policy instruments indicate a growing recognition of the need to balance biodiversity conservation with agricultural development. By embracing the principles of the Nature Futures Framework, Cameroon can chart a path toward a future where nature and society thrive together.

3.1.1.2 Life Frames Framework

The sustainability of biodiversity and agriculture in Cameroon is governed by a range of national-level policies that reflect varying priorities and values. Applying the Life Frames Framework (LFF) which includes the 'living from,' 'living in,' 'living with,' and 'living as' frames, offers a comprehensive lens through which to examine the underlying values and orientations in these policies (Table 3).

Table 3 Application of LFF to the biodiversity and agricultural policy instruments of Cameroon

Policy document	Living from	Living in	Living with	Living as
GESP 2010–2019	High	Medium	High	Low
NDS30	High	Medium	High	Low
Vision 2035	High	High	High	Low
NBSAP II	High	High	High	Medium
PRSP 2003	High	High	High	Low
NDCs 2021	High	Medium	High	Low
NBESA 2022	High	High	High	Medium
State of BFA 2015	High	High	High	Low

The GESP is primarily rooted in the 'living from' frame, as it promotes economic growth through agricultural modernization, increased productivity, and value-chain development. This approach positions nature as a resource base for human prosperity. While the strategy acknowledges the importance of rural livelihoods, it offers limited insight into cultural or community-based perspectives, thus only marginally engaging the 'living in' frame. It also introduces environmental sustainability as a development condition, reflecting some alignment with the 'living with' frame. However, there is minimal to no engagement with Indigenous or ontological worldviews, making the 'living as' dimension virtually absent.

The NDS30 continues the economic trajectory set by GESP, emphasizing the instrumental use of biodiversity and land for national development, which aligns strongly with the 'living from' frame. The policy also references community resilience and inclusive development, touching upon the 'living in' frame. Environmental concerns are integrated through commitments to ecosystem conservation and sustainable agriculture, reflecting the 'living with' frame. However, like its predecessor, NDS30 lacks an explicit recognition of Indigenous knowledge systems or ontologies, indicating limited engagement with the 'living as' frame.

As the country's long-term development roadmap, Vision 2035 firmly anchors the 'living from' frame, emphasizing agriculture's role in poverty reduction and economic growth. It also addresses social cohesion and community development, thus partly embracing the 'living in' perspective. Environmental conservation is promoted as essential for sustainable development, aligning with the 'living with' frame. Nonetheless, the policy remains largely silent on deeper ecological or spiritual relationships with nature, and thus does not substantially reflect the 'living as' frame.

NBSAP II offers one of the most comprehensive recognitions of biodiversity's multi-dimensional value. It fully integrates the 'living from' frame by acknowledging biodiversity's contributions to food security and livelihoods. The strategy also respects local cultural practices and encourages community involvement in conservation, engaging the 'living in' frame. The 'living with' frame is strongly represented through the plan's goals to maintain ecosystem integrity and promote sustainable use. While the 'living as' frame is not central, there is a moderate acknowledgment of traditional knowledge and moral obligations to nature, hinting at a more holistic worldview.

The Poverty Reduction and Strategy Paper PRSP 2003 adopts a 'living from' perspective by focusing on agricultural development as a pathway out of poverty. It recognizes the social dimensions of agriculture, aligning with the 'living in' frame. Although sustainability is addressed through land and water resource management, the 'living with' frame is only modestly represented. Like many of Cameroon's older policies, the 'living as' frame is absent, as Indigenous ecological perspectives were not integrated into the development discourse at the time.

Cameroon's NDCs reflect a strong 'living from' orientation by linking biodiversity conservation and reforestation to climate mitigation and agricultural adaptation. They also hint at the 'living in' frame by acknowledging the importance of ecosystem services for communities. The 'living with' frame is more pronounced, as the document emphasizes nature-based solutions and ecosystem resilience. However, the 'living as' perspective is not explicitly considered, and Indigenous knowledge systems receive only limited attention.

NBESA presents one of the most balanced integrations of the LFF. It clearly supports the 'living from' frame by quantifying the economic contributions of biodiversity. The 'living in' frame is evident in its emphasis on the cultural significance of ecosystems and the importance of community engagement. The 'living with' frame is central, as the assessment promotes conservation and ecosystem health. Though the 'living as' frame is not a dominant theme, there is growing recognition of Indigenous values and worldviews, offering potential for deeper integration in the future.

The State of Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture Policy Report by MINADER emphasizes the role of biodiversity in sustaining food systems and agricultural productivity, aligning it strongly with the 'living from' frame. It acknowledges traditional farming practices and local crop varieties, engaging the 'living in' frame. The report also supports sustainable agricultural practices, reflecting the 'living with' perspective. However, similar to other sectoral reports, it does not address Indigenous cosmologies or spiritual relationships with the land, leaving the 'living as' frame unaddressed.

Cameroon's National Adaptation Plan (NAP) aligns closely with the 'living from' frame through its focus on maintaining agricultural outputs amid climate stress. It also incorporates the 'living in' frame by recognizing the social vulnerability of rural communities. The 'living with' frame is evident in the promotion of ecosystem-based adaptation and sustainable land use. Nonetheless, there is no

substantial engagement with Indigenous epistemologies or spiritual values, making the 'living as' frame weak.

Thus, an analysis of Cameroon's biodiversity and agricultural policy landscape through the Life Frames Framework reveals a predominant orientation toward the 'living from' frame, with nature largely seen as a means of sustaining human livelihoods and economic growth. The 'living in' and 'living with' frames appear to be gaining traction, especially in newer documents that recognize the importance of culture and ecological integrity. However, the 'living as' frame, which emphasizes ontological interdependence and kinship with nature, remains largely unexplored. Integrating Indigenous ontologies and ethical relationships with nature into future policy frameworks would allow Cameroon to adopt a more holistic and inclusive approach to biodiversity and agricultural sustainability.

3.1.2 Desk-based study of government investments

Between 2010 and 2020, Cameroon's national budget reflected a strategic prioritization of agricultural development and biodiversity conservation, aligning with key policy documents such as the Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP) 2010–2019, the National Development Strategy 2020–2030 (NDS30), Vision 2035, and various sector-specific plans.

This analysis examines the allocation of financial resources to ministries such as the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER), the Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development (MINEPDED), the Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife (MINFOF), and the Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development (MINEPAT), identifying the relative emphasis placed on agricultural production and biodiversity conservation (Table 4).

Table 4 Main sources of public funding for agriculture and biodiversity conservation in Cameroon

Ministry	Focus area	Budget emphasis (2010–2020)
MINADER	Agricultural Production	High
MINEPDED	Biodiversity Conservation	Moderate
MINFOF	Forest Management and Wildlife	Moderate
MINEPAT	Policy Coordination and Strategy Implementation	High

Table 4 illustrates that while all ministries contributed to the national objectives, MINADER received the highest budget emphasis, reflecting the government's prioritization of agricultural development. MINEPDED and MINFOF, while important, received comparatively lower allocations, indicating a secondary focus on biodiversity conservation and forest management.

Vision 2035 envisions Cameroon as an emerging, democratic, and united country, with a focus on reducing poverty, achieving middle-income status, and ensuring sustainable development. The GESP (2010–2019) aimed to accelerate growth and employment, emphasizing infrastructure development, rural sector modernization, and environmental sustainability. The NDS30 (2020–2030) continued these objectives, with an added emphasis on climate change adaptation, biodiversity conservation, and inclusive economic growth.

According to the IMF Staff Country Reports, the allocation to the rural sector increased from 5.1% in 2009 to 6.6% by 2020, reflecting a sustained commitment to agricultural development. Similarly, the productive infrastructure sector, which includes investments in agriculture-related infrastructure, maintained a steady share of approximately 18.3% of the total budget.

MINADER's budget allocations during this period demonstrate a clear focus on agricultural production. For instance, in 2015, the ministry received approximately 108.7 billion CFA francs, with

significant portions dedicated to modernizing rural infrastructure and sustainable land management practices. Specific programs included the rehabilitation of farm-to-market roads, provision of agricultural inputs, and support for value chain development in crops like cocoa, cotton, and palm oil.

MINEPDED's budget allocations during this period indicate a moderate focus on biodiversity conservation. Projects funded included the protection of water resources, development of biosafety frameworks, and implementation of biodiversity conservation initiatives in regions such as the East and South Regions. However, the financial resources allocated to these projects were relatively limited compared to those directed towards agricultural development.

While specific budget figures for MINFOF during this period are not available, the Ministry's activities, such as the implementation of the Forest/Environment Sector Program (PSFE), received support from international partners like the World Bank and the Global Environment Facility. These initiatives focused on sustainable forest management and biodiversity conservation, aligning with national objectives outlined in the GESP and Vision 2035.

MINEPAT played a pivotal role in coordinating and monitoring the implementation of national development strategies, including the GESP and NDS30. The ministry's budget allocations supported the formulation of policies and programs that integrated agricultural development and environmental sustainability, ensuring alignment with the overarching national vision.

Thus, between 2010 and 2020, Cameroon's national budget allocations underscored a strong commitment to agricultural production, with MINADER receiving the most significant financial resources. Biodiversity conservation, though acknowledged in policy documents, received relatively less emphasis in terms of financial allocations. This trend suggests a need for a more balanced approach in future budgeting to ensure that both agricultural development and biodiversity conservation are adequately supported, in line with the objectives of the GESP, NDS30, and Vision 2035. It is therefore recommended that future budget allocations should:

- Increase financial resources allocated to MINEPDED and MINFOF to support biodiversity conservation initiatives, aligning with national and international commitments.
- Develop and implement policies that integrate agricultural development with environmental sustainability, ensuring that both sectors are mutually reinforcing.
- Establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of budget allocations and ensure that resources are utilized efficiently to achieve desired outcomes.
- Engage local communities, civil society organizations, and the private sector in the planning and implementation of agricultural and environmental programs to ensure inclusivity and sustainability.
- Invest in capacity building for institutions involved in agricultural and environmental management to enhance their ability to plan, implement, and monitor projects effectively.

Table 5 Amounts allocated (in Euros) to different Cameroonian ministries and evolution over time

Ministry	Estimated Budget (2015)	Key Focus Areas / Funded Policies	Trend (2010–2020)	Remarks
MINADER (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)	€165.7 million (approx. 108.7 billion CFA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cocoa and Coffee Sector Plan (2014) - Rural infrastructure rehabilitation - Agricultural input provision - Support for value chains (cocoa, cotton, palm oil) 	Increasing (5.1% of national budget in 2009 to 6.6% in 2020)	Top priority sector; reflects strong emphasis on food security and economic growth
MINEPDED (Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development)	€27.4 million (approx. 18 billion CFA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NDCs (2021) - NBESA (2022) - Biosafety frameworks - Water resource protection 	Moderate increase, but low overall allocation	Undervalued relative to policy ambitions; requires more funding for biodiversity commitments
MINFOF (Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife)	€18.3 million (approx. 12 billion CFA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REDD+ Strategy (2018) - Forest/Environment Sector Programme (PSFE) - Sustainable forest management 	Flat; dependent on international support	Co-financed by donors (e.g., GEF, World Bank); national budget share remains limited
MINEPAT (Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development)	N/A (Planning and coordination role)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GESP (2010–2019) - NDS30 (2020–2030) - Vision 2035 implementation monitoring 	Strategic coordinator across sectors	Not a direct implementing ministry, but central to planning and budget guidance

Table 5 highlights the distribution of public investments across key ministries in Cameroon from 2010 to 2020, emphasizing the government's policy priorities between agricultural production and biodiversity conservation. The data, converted to euros for comparability, clearly indicates that MINADER (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development) received the largest share of financial resources, with an estimated allocation of €165.7 million in 2015 alone. This substantial funding underscores the centrality of agriculture to national development strategies, particularly under the Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP), Vision 2035, and the National Development Strategy 2020–2030 (NDS30). Key agricultural programs funded through MINADER included rural infrastructure development (notably farm-to-market roads), input provision for farmers, and support for high-value crop value chains such as cocoa, cotton, and palm oil.

In contrast, MINEPDED (Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development), which is responsible for biodiversity conservation and environmental protection, received significantly less funding, approximately €27.4 million. While MINEPDED spearheaded major national and international environmental commitments such as the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs, 2021), the National Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Assessment (NBESA, 2022), and national biosafety frameworks, the low financial allocation suggests that biodiversity conservation remains a secondary concern in budgetary terms, despite its strategic importance in national policy.

Similarly, MINFOF (Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife) received a modest budget estimate of €18.3 million, mainly supported by external partners such as the World Bank and the Global Environment Facility. Its core initiatives, including the REDD+ Strategy (2018) and the Forest and Environment Sector Programme (PSFE), focused on sustainable forest management and biodiversity protection. However, the reliance on international financing indicates limited domestic prioritization within the national budget.

MINEPAT (Ministry of Economy, Planning and Regional Development) plays a critical planning and coordination role, overseeing the alignment of policies under Vision 2035 and NDS30. Although it does not directly implement sectoral programs, its influence in shaping budget priorities is significant.

Thus, Table 7 reveals a strong policy–investment alignment in favour of agricultural development, with biodiversity and forestry receiving comparatively limited fiscal attention. This imbalance highlights the need for a more integrated approach that supports both food security and environmental sustainability, ensuring Cameroon meets its development and conservation goals concurrently.

3.1.3 Stakeholder Interviews

Stakeholder mapping

In Cameroon, five government ministries govern and seek to influence agriculture and biodiversity, each with their own policies, which are briefly described.

The Ministry of Economy, Planning and Land Planning (MINEPAT) is responsible for land-use planning, including land titles. However, the majority of agricultural land, including for tree crops such as cocoa, are under customary land rights and not formalised (Folefack and Darr, 2021).

The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER) aims to double national cocoa production from 300,000 to 600,000 tons by 2030 via ‘sustainable farm expansion’, improving cocoa yields by providing improved hybrid cocoa seedling to registered farmers, providing fertilizers and pesticides and training farmers on good agricultural practices (Office of the Prime Minister, 2014). These activities are implemented by Société de Développement du Cacao (SODECAO), reporting to MINADER, a parastatal promoting cocoa production, and the PAD-CACAO program, via farmer groups, such as cooperatives and Common Initiative Groups. MINADER recommends planting 1200 cocoa trees per hectare, although they recognise farmers often plant more, and to practice selective tree felling before planting. The National Agricultural Investment Plan 2020-2030 sees cocoa as the future, allocating 40.000 million CFA of investment, although the Fonds de Développement des Filières Cacao et Café, allocated the PAD CACAO program only 569 million CFA in 2021 (FODECC, 2021).

The Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife (MINFOF) is responsible for the management and protection of forests. It manages the Forest & Environment Sector program and budget. Under the 2024 Forest Law, farmers should obtain permission from MINFOF before cutting trees of economic value in their farms, and slash and burn is not permitted. MINFOF indicated that many farmers do not obtain permission before cutting trees but burning is more respected although some livestock and cocoa farmers engage in bush burning to open new fields or convert fallow.

The Ministry of Environment, Nature Protection and Sustainable Development (MINEPDED) collaborates with MINFOF concerning agriculture, such as fallow forest burning and tree felling (Ministère de environnement de la Protection de la Nature et du Développement Durable, 2018) and regarding the 2018 national emissions reduction strategy that addresses deforestation and degradation (Ministère de l’Environnement de la Protection de la Nature et du Développement Durable, 2018) They promote agriculture without agrochemicals or in small quantities. Cameroon

has a list of chemicals approved by MINEPDED and MINADER, although in practice, non-authorized farm inputs can be found in the market and many farmers are not aware of the regulations or are unable to follow application guidelines on some imported chemicals due to low literacy or due to instructions provided on inputs being in foreign languages. An environmental impact assessment (EIA) is required for large farms (>100 ha); however, no cocoa farms of this size were known in the area. The average farm size is around 4 hectares, although some larger farms up to 20 ha exist.

The Ministry of Commerce (MINCommerce), under which the National Cocoa and Coffee Board (ONCC) has operated since 1991, publish daily trading prices for cocoa and perform post-harvest quality checks of cocoa sold by traders. The tax of 25 000 F CFA/ton on exported cocoa is used to fund this work, as well as supporting the cocoa sector platform, the Conseil Interprofessionnel du Cacao et du Café (CICC) and providing development funds through the Fonds de Développement des Filières Cacao – Café (FODECC). Recently funded projects in collaboration with Ministry of Research and Innovation (MINRESI) and the Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD) have focused on increasing the quantity and quality of cocoa production pre- and post-harvest. In February 2023 the first session of the multi-stakeholder consultation platform “Sustainable Cocoa Committee in Cameroon” between MINADER and MINCommerce and public and private sector, civil society, and research representatives took place, up until end 2024. This has aimed to implement the “Roadmap to deforestation free cocoa”, an initiative financed and supported by the Dutch-based government, private and donor funded organisation Sustainable Trade Initiative (IDH) (IDH, 2021, 2023). This has been a turning point from previously when none of the government stakeholders had policies which explicitly addressed biodiversity, forests and cocoa.

Stakeholder interview results

The stakeholder interviews conducted in Lomie, Meyomessala, and Somalomo with administrative authorities, sectoral delegates, traditional leaders, local NGOs, women’s groups, farming cooperatives, and individual community members (Table 8), revealed deep-rooted systemic gaps in how biodiversity and agriculture are conceptualized and managed. Using a thematic approach, the following analysis outlines the major themes that emerged, supported by direct quotes to illustrate the voices of those most engaged in the sectors.

Table 6 Stakeholders interviewed in Cameroon

Community	Name	Organization / Institution	Stakeholder Type	Position / Role	Date of Interview
Lomie	MANONGA Pierre	Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife (MINFOF) – Lomie Sub-Division	Government (Sectoral Delegate)	Forestry and Wildlife Delegate	22-05-2024
	KEUMLE Bruce Samuel	ASTRADHE (Local NGO)	Civil Society / NGO	Program Coordinator	22-05-2024
	Sandjuoh Valerie	Women's Farming Cooperative – Lomie	Local Cooperative / Women's Group	President	23-05-2024
	Ntoudou Messi Arbogaste	ASTRADHE	Civil Society / NGO	Field Technician	23-05-2024
	Chief Atangana Jean	Traditional Council – Lomie	Traditional Leader	Chief of Village	23-05-2024

Community	Name	Organization / Institution	Stakeholder Type	Position / Role	Date of Interview
	Nguime Dominique	Individual Farmer – Lomié	Local Community Member	Cocoa and Plantain Farmer	23-05-2024
Somalomo	NGUEME Joseph	MINEPDED (Ministry of Environment)	Government (Sectoral Delegate)	Divisional Delegate	25-05-2024
	DJOBOUT Thomas	Traditional Council – Somalomo	Traditional Leader	Paramount Chief	25-05-2024
	BEKOUA Jean Robert	Somalomo Council	Local Administration	Mayor	26-05-2024
	NGOH Sidonie	Women's Cooperative – Somalomo	Women's Group	Treasurer	26-05-2024
	NGONO Christelle	Youth Association “Nature Verte”	Local NGO / Youth Group	Coordinator	26-05-2024
	EBANGA Denis	Individual Farmer – Somalomo	Local Community Member	Cocoa Farmer	26-05-2024
Meyomessala	MBARGA Théophile	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER)	Government (Sectoral Delegate)	Agricultural Extension Officer	28-05-2024
	MBOUKO Jean-Claude	Ministry of Forestry and Wildlife (MINFOF)	Government (Sectoral Delegate)	Forestry Delegate	29-05-2024
	NGOUPA Thérèse	Women's Cooperative – Meyomessala	Women's Group / Cooperative	President	28-05-2024
	ESSONO Albert	Traditional Council – Meyomessala	Traditional Leader	Village Chief	29-05-2024
	BEKONO Suzanne	NGO “EcoDéveloppement Cameroun”	Local NGO	Director	29-05-2024
	NKODO Marcel	Cocoa Farmers' Union – Meyomessala	Farming Cooperative	Secretary-General	29-05-2024
	OWONA Rosine	Individual Farmer – Meyomessala	Local Community Member	Smallholder Farmer	29-05-2024

Across all interviewed stakeholders, there was broad consensus that the agricultural and biodiversity sectors have evolved as “two separate worlds,” often operating in isolation despite their spatial and ecological overlap. A sub-divisional official in the Ministry of Agriculture in Meyomessala remarked that “*We work in agriculture, but we rarely coordinate with the forestry or environment services, unless there is a conflict*”. Meanwhile a Chief of Forestry Post in Somalomo noted that “*Conservation is our mission. The agricultural guys are focused on crops and yields. We only meet when farmers encroach on protected areas*”. This institutional siloing has created operational and policy fragmentation, leading to conflicting land use objectives. Biodiversity policies, where they exist, are seen to operate more as regulatory impositions than collaborative frameworks.

A dominant theme [VII] [PN2] among farmers was the strong prioritization of agricultural productivity over biodiversity conservation. For most rural stakeholders, especially farmers and women's groups, food security and income were understandably placed above ecological concerns. The leader of a women's farming cooperative in Lomie said *"We cannot talk about protecting animals and trees when our children are hungry"*. This view was echoed by a senior representative from an agricultural parastatal, who said *"There is political pressure to increase food production. Biodiversity is important, but it does not feed the nation"*. The view here reveals an instrumental and utilitarian understanding of land, where conservation is only considered if it directly supports productivity goals.

While biodiversity protection laws and strategies such as the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) are acknowledged, many stakeholders questioned their tangible impact at the grassroots level. A traditional chief in Meyomessala remarked that *"We have laws and plans, but they stay in Yaoundé. We need actions that change lives, not just papers"*. The head of a common imitative group operating in Somalomo highlighted the disconnect between policy symbolism and practical implementation. He remarked *"The policy language is elegant i.e., 'ecosystem services,' 'resilience,' and so on, but on the ground, there is no funding or follow-up"*. Even administrative officials agreed that biodiversity policies often function more as a form of international compliance than community-driven tools.

Despite diverging priorities, many stakeholders shared a common desire for a more sustainable and inclusive future. While local farmers focused on practical support, tools, seeds, access to markets, traditional leaders and civil society actors pushed for a broader vision. A young leader of a farming group in Somalomo noted that *"We can protect nature if we are also given a future in farming"*. A delegate from MINFOF in Lomie shared the same perspective by noting *"What we need is a policy that sees biodiversity not just as forest animals, but as part of our agricultural landscape."* This convergence of views hints at a readiness among stakeholders for an integrated approach that values biodiversity as more than a conservation object, but as a co-driver of agricultural resilience and livelihood sustainability.

Perhaps the most forward-looking theme was a call from many stakeholders [VI3] [PN4] (administrative authorities, sectoral delegates, traditional leaders, and local NGOs) to reframe biodiversity as a productive asset rather than a restrictive burden. There was strong advocacy for agroecology, sustainable land use planning, and participatory policy design. A woman farmer and healer in Meyomessala remarked that *"We must stop seeing nature as something separate from us. The forest is not only for animals; it is our pharmacy, our soil, our water"*. This perspective was shared by the head of an NGO in Lomie who stated that *"If biodiversity policies embraced rural livelihoods instead of limiting them, we would have more allies in conservation"*.

Thus, these interviews reveal a shared concern: the failure of current policy structures to bridge the needs of agricultural development with those of biodiversity conservation. While agricultural productivity dominates in both discourse and practice, there is clear support across stakeholder groups for a more integrated, practical, and inclusive approach. Policies must evolve to reflect the lived realities of rural communities, moving from symbolic conservation to synergistic land use planning. A strategic reimagining, one that embraces biodiversity as both ecological heritage and livelihood asset, is urgently needed for the future of Cameroon's rural and environmental policy.

3.1.4 Discussion

The findings from Cameroon's biodiversity and agricultural policy arena and its stakeholders reveal a complex but increasingly deliberate effort to reconcile ecological sustainability with economic development (Ze and Zhao, 2018; Fabre et al., 2022). Using a multi-framework analysis, including discourse analysis, the Nature Futures Framework (NFF), the Life Frames Framework (LFF), and stakeholder interviews, we present how national policies conceptualize biodiversity and agriculture, and where opportunities and gaps remain.

Cameroon's policy evolution, as captured in key documents such as the Growth and Employment Strategy Paper (GESP), National Development Strategy 2020–2030 (NDS30), Vision 2035, and the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan II (NBSAP II), reflects a growing recognition of the importance of environmental sustainability in achieving national development goals. Early policy instruments, such as the GESP, prioritized agricultural modernization for poverty reduction with only peripheral references to environmental concerns. In contrast, the NDS30 and Vision 2035 integrate biodiversity more centrally, reflecting an emerging shift toward more holistic development planning. However, while biodiversity is increasingly acknowledged, agriculture continues to dominate both in discourse and investment, as revealed in the budgetary allocations where the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER) consistently receives higher financial support compared to the Ministry of Environment (MINEPDED) or Forestry and Wildlife (MINFOF). This budgetary emphasis aligns with the predominant policy orientation identified through the Life Frames Framework, where a strong “living from” narrative underscores most national strategies. Nature is largely framed as a resource for economic growth and food security. While this framing is pragmatic, particularly in the context of poverty and demographic pressure, it risks sidelining more integrated or ethical relationships with nature. The “living in” and “living with” frames are moderately represented, particularly in newer documents like the NBESA 2022 and NBSAP II, which emphasize community engagement and ecosystem services. However, the “living as” frame, which embodies Indigenous and spiritual values of unity with nature, remains marginal across all major policy documents.

The analysis using the Nature Futures Framework (NFF) complements this by showing how Cameroonian policies engage with nature's intrinsic, instrumental, and relational values. The “Nature for Nature” perspective is embedded in NBSAP II and NBESA, with commitments to reforestation and community conservation. “Nature for Society” is reflected in the NDCs, Vision 2035, and adaptation strategies that tie biodiversity to food security and climate resilience. The “Nature as Culture” dimension is acknowledged in principle, especially in references to traditional knowledge and gender inclusion, but is weakly operationalized in policy implementation. As such, while the conceptual frameworks exist within policy texts, actual practice tends to be top-down and sectorally fragmented.

Stakeholder interviews deepened this insight by exposing the disconnect between policy intent and implementation. Respondents across administrative, traditional, and grassroots institutions unanimously highlighted institutional siloing as a critical barrier to integration. Agriculture and biodiversity sectors often operate independently, with coordination occurring only in conflict situations, such as encroachment into protected areas. This institutional fragmentation reinforces the perception of biodiversity policies as regulatory rather than supportive, exacerbating local resistance and limiting impact.

Furthermore, stakeholders emphasized a utilitarian view of nature, shaped by urgent livelihood needs. For many rural communities, biodiversity is only valuable if it contributes directly to household survival. This perception reflects the policy and investment imbalance: conservation is rarely presented as economically beneficial or integrated into development incentives. Nonetheless, there is an emerging grassroots consensus that a better balance is possible. From women's cooperatives to forestry officials and NGO representatives, there is growing support for agroecology, nature-based solutions, and participatory land use planning that bridge conservation with productivity. This is a critical entry point for future policy reform. Mechanisms that enable diverse farmer's voices, perspectives, framing of discourses and inherent problems and solutions to be better heard and considered could counter the current misalignment of national and international policies with practices.

As Ingram et al (2025) indicate, key stakeholders and state and private sector policies, at national, regional and international scales, are not well aligned. For example, around cocoa and forests, a coalescence of government and market-based stakeholder's forest and (agroforestry) cocoa policies and programs are now slowly emerging because of international pressure, such as the Roadmap to

Sustainable Cocoa, and Cocoa Talks organised in the light of the European Union Deforestation Regulation. International and national discourses on the relations between agriculture (such as cocoa) and biodiversity (notably in forests) could be aligned, nationally and internationally. Implicit trade-offs in policies and discourses need to be made explicit, and aligned with the impact pathways underlying forest, deforestation and cocoa policies, and conscious, cross-sectoral choices made about equitable, acceptable balances for the different stakeholders between forest conservation and cocoa farming livelihoods.

Given rural stakeholders' low awareness and scepticism towards agriculture and biodiversity policies, better communication and support is essential for effective implementation or potential revision. Other studies have similar findings about incoherences and incongruences between stakeholders, their practices, initiatives, and policies, particularly concerning (zero)deforestation and biodiversity loss. Vogel et al., (2020) found that perceptions towards future transitions are not actively coordinated in Cameroon. Mithöfer et al., (2024) compared Cameroon, Peru, and Indonesia, finding that policies and development programs focus on expansion and productivity increases, irrespective of smallholder needs for economically viable farming systems and market structures resulting in little farmer bargaining power. Sustainability standards are spread unevenly, and competing interests and interdependencies between different actors' responses to concerns are not openly acknowledged by public and private sectors. The lack of power, with voices of smallholders largely unheard, especially women and youth (Nangia & Forsac-Tata 2024).

The discourse analysis and frameworks collectively demonstrate that while biodiversity is increasingly present in national planning, agriculture remains the central axis of Cameroon's development agenda. This prioritization, while understandable, limits the transformative potential of sustainability-focused policies. For meaningful progress, policies must move beyond rhetorical integration toward institutional coherence, where agriculture and biodiversity are managed not as parallel agendas but as interdependent systems.

3.1.5 Recommendations

To achieve this, several strategic shifts are necessary:

1. Financial investments in biodiversity-related ministries must increase to match the ambitions outlined in the NDS30 and international commitments like the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).
2. Institutional mechanisms for cross-sectoral coordination, particularly between MINADER, MINFOF, and MINEPDED, must be strengthened to align planning and implementation.
3. Indigenous knowledge systems and local cultural values should be more actively embedded in policy design through genuine community participation.
4. Monitoring and evaluation systems must track not just outputs but the socio-ecological impacts of integrated policy initiatives.

Challenges to implement policies are high. These include weak enforcement and ability to scale down to local level due to a lack of presence in rural areas, fragmented policy implementation, lack of co-ordination and alignment between sectors and Ministries, corruption, lack of knowledge of policy on the ground (i.e. in the field and forests) and limited financing (Ingram et al 2025). Achieving the country's development and conservation goals will require strengthened inter-sectoral coordination, inclusive governance, and increased investment in sustainable practices that align biodiversity protection with the needs of rural communities and economic growth.

Cameroon therefore stands at a pivotal moment. The frameworks and discourse are evolving in the right direction, and there is both institutional and grassroots appetite for change. However, without deliberate structural reforms and investment alignment, the gap between biodiversity conservation and agricultural development will persist. A paradigm shift, viewing biodiversity as both ecological infrastructure and livelihood asset, is essential to building a resilient and inclusive future for Cameroon.

3.2 Colombia

3.2.1 Discourse analysis

In Colombia, the primary policy documents issued by the national government that outline national-level strategies for biodiversity conservation and agricultural production are the **National Policy for the Integral Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services (NBP)** and the **National Development Plans (NDPs)**.

The **National Policy for the Integrated Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services (NBP)** from 2012 is a state policy designed to promote the integrated management of biodiversity and ecosystem services at national, regional, local, and transboundary levels. This policy functions as a strategic framework for all environmental management instruments—encompassing policies, regulations, plans, programs, and projects—whether currently implemented or under development, ensuring the effective conservation of biodiversity across different organizational levels.

The **National Development Plan (NDP)** is the central planning instrument prepared by each administration at the beginning of its four-year term. It serves as the legal and formal foundation for establishing government priorities. The NDP defines the objectives, strategies, and policy guidelines that shape the country's development agenda during a presidential term. It plays a pivotal role in steering national policy direction and aligning public investments with strategic goals. Between 2010 and 2020, three National Development Plans were formulated:

- The 2010–2014 National Development Plan: "Prosperity for All"
- The 2014–2018 Plan: "Everyone for a New Country"
- The 2018–2022 Plan: "Pact for Colombia, Pact for Equity"

3.2.1.1 Nature Futures Framework

Analyzing these public policy instruments through the lens of the **Nature Futures Framework** reveals the different ways in which these policies value nature, as well as which perspectives are prioritized. Figure 2 Policies from NBP and NDPs associated with Nature for Nature, Nature for Society, and Nature as Culture perspectives below illustrates the total number of policies from NBP and NDPs associated with Nature for Nature, Nature for Society, and Nature as Culture perspectives¹. Each point in the chart represents a specific policy, categorized based on whether it aligns with one of the perspectives or a combination of them. The majority of the policies (26) emphasize an **instrumental value** of nature, aligning predominantly with the *Nature for Society* perspective, where nature is valued primarily for the benefits it provides to human well-being, such as ecosystem services and economic development. A smaller number of policies (3) incorporate **relational values**, reflecting a recognition of the deep social and cultural connections people have with nature, consistent with the *Nature as Culture* perspective. Only one policy reflects an **intrinsic value** of nature—*Nature for Nature*—which acknowledges the inherent worth of nature, independent of human use or benefit. In terms of combined perspectives, the most frequently observed pairings are *Nature for Nature–for Society* (3 policies) and *Nature as Culture–for Society* (3 policies), suggesting some effort to integrate different value frameworks. However, only one policy reflects

¹ See Annex 1 for the Nature Futures Framework table with corresponding policies

the less common combination of *Nature for Nature*–as *Culture*, indicating limited integration of intrinsic and cultural values in most policies analyzed.

Figure 2 Policies from NBP and NDPs associated with Nature for Nature, Nature for Society, and Nature as Culture perspectives

With this overarching perspective, each policy instrument is analyzed separately and thoroughly. The **National Policy for the Integrated Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services, produced by the Ministry of the Environment** primarily reflects the *Nature for Society* perspective. It emphasizes the instrumental value of biodiversity, portraying it as the foundation for ecosystem services that are essential to Colombia’s well-being, development, and long-term economic sustainability. In this instrument, biodiversity is portrayed as a resource, as an entity external to humans, and as the essential guarantor of ecosystem functions that directly support human activities. This perspective is articulated in the policy, which states: *“It acknowledges the strategic importance of biodiversity as the primary source, foundation, and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that support the country’s development, underpin its competitiveness, and are fundamental to the well-being of Colombian society.”* In other words, the focus rests upon the benefits of Nature for humans.

Only one section of the policy reflects an intrinsic value of nature, stating that “Life is the ultimate value. The survival of life on the planet depends on the protection of both the tangible and intangible components of biodiversity, as well as an understanding of its dynamic nature.” However, this is the sole instance, and overall, the core of the policy frames biodiversity primarily as a strategic asset. Its value is largely portrayed in terms of its capacity to support and enhance human livelihoods and economic activities. By emphasizing biodiversity’s role in delivering ecosystem services, the policy highlights its utilitarian benefits, such as supporting agriculture, ensuring water availability, regulating the climate, and driving economic productivity. These services are presented as essential to Colombia’s long-term competitiveness and sustainable development.

While the policy centers on the instrumental value of biodiversity, it also acknowledges and incorporates some interpretations of the *Nature as Culture* perspective. This perspective highlights the deep, intrinsic connection between Colombia’s biological diversity and its rich ethnic and cultural heritage. As the policy notes: *“This close relationship, manifested at various scales, is*

understood as the interdependent connection between ecological systems and social systems, where biodiversity shapes culture, and culture, in turn, transforms and structures the spatial arrangement of biodiversity." This interpretation recognizes that there are cultural dimensions to Nature, but does not extend as far as a relational ontology, common to many Indigenous ontologies, which collapses rigid distinctions between pre-existing entities of coupled humans and Nature and instead envisions living assemblages, often with sacred dimensions.

This recognition of biodiversity's cultural dimension (as far as it goes) highlights how the natural environment has historically shaped the identities, traditions, and livelihoods of Colombia's diverse communities. However, while the policy acknowledges these intrinsic cultural values, it primarily frames them as supporting tools for the broader objective of sustaining ecosystem services. This positioning suggests that the cultural connections to biodiversity are important primarily because they enhance the effectiveness of conservation strategies at local scales. The policy states: *"Biodiversity should be recognized as the principal structuring element of territorial planning processes, serving as the source and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that are crucial for the development and sustainability of human activities related to production, extraction, settlement, and consumption."* In this way, the policy explicitly links biodiversity to the functionality and sustainability of human activities, placing its value squarely within the Nature for Society framework.

The policy does not promote biodiversity outside of its instrumental value in supporting ecosystem services. Instead, it maintains a consistent focus on how biodiversity underpins human well-being, economic growth, and development. The environmental stewardship in Colombia has historically been relegated to the environmental sector, effectively isolating biodiversity management from broader governance and development processes. To address this, the policy proposes a paradigm shift: rather than treating environmental management as the sole responsibility of environmental agencies, all sectors of governance and development must recognize their dependency on biodiversity and ecosystem services. The policy underscores not only the need for integration across sectors, but a shift in mindset is required, where biodiversity is no longer seen as an isolated environmental issue but as a foundational element of societal well-being. The policy seeks to create a governance model where biodiversity and ecosystem services are prioritized as integral to all sectors of development, ensuring a sustainable future in the face of growing demands for ecosystem services.

The analysis of the **National Development Plans (NDPs)** reveals that the discourse surrounding nature predominantly emphasizes its instrumental value, especially within the context of agricultural policies. Within these instruments, nature is framed as an economic asset, with an emphasis on land as a resource for agricultural production, devoid of any acknowledgment of its agency or relational value. For instance, the PNDs promote the "utilization of public vacant lands" for economic activities. This is further illustrated by policies allowing "ownership of lands that were originally allocated as public vacant lands or acquired through comprehensive land subsidies, even if this results in consolidated properties with areas exceeding the limits set for Family Agricultural Units, provided that the properties in question are part of an agricultural or forestry development project". Such provisions aim to enable beneficiaries to leverage land as an asset to initiate income-generating activities, reinforcing the instrumental value of nature within agricultural policy.

For specific ecosystems, such as wetlands and *páramos*,² both intrinsic and instrumental values are acknowledged. Regarding intrinsic value, "In areas designated as páramos, agricultural activities, exploration or exploitation of non-renewable natural resources, and the construction of hydrocarbon refineries are not permitted." These ecosystems are recognized for their inherent ecological importance alongside their utility in supporting human and economic activities. This dual recognition highlights a nuanced approach in policies targeting these critical ecosystems, albeit

² Paramos are a Neotropical high mountain biome with vegetation composed mainly of giant rosette plants, shrubs and grasses, fundamental for water cycling and filtration. Although they only occupy 1.7% of Colombia's land, they produce 85% of its fresh water.

limited in scope to specific cases. It contrasts with references to public vacant lands, where the PNDs do not specify the ecosystems present in these areas, overlooking their potential ecological significance.

The "Nature as Culture" perspective appears only in limited contexts in the PNDs, specifically in reference to Indigenous Peoples and local rural communities practicing ancestral traditions. However, this cultural dimension is not integrated into the broader policy framework and remains confined to specific cases. For example, the PNDs mention that "agreements with vulnerable rural populations who inhabit, occupy, or engage in traditional practices associated with the rural economy in protected areas, deriving their livelihood from these practices, will be recognized by the entities that enter into agreements." Additionally, the plans aim to "generate sectoral agendas aimed at strengthening competitive and sustainable value chains, allowing for the creation of mechanisms and alternatives for the appropriate and responsible use of the environment and natural resources, as well as protecting biodiversity and the traditional knowledge of Indigenous communities in the Amazon." Despite these limited acknowledgments to 'traditional practices' and 'traditional knowledge', the cultural dimension of nature remains peripheral, often framed through economic and livelihood lenses, rather than valuing Indigenous-kinship relations with land, for example, and hence with limited integration into the overarching policy narratives.

In conclusion, the analysis of the National Development Plans (PNDs) reveals a dominant framing of nature through an instrumental lens, particularly within agricultural policies. Nature is primarily viewed as an economic asset, with policies focusing on land as a resource for production, often neglecting its ecological and relational value. While specific ecosystems like wetlands and páramos receive a more nuanced recognition, acknowledging both their intrinsic and instrumental value, this approach remains limited in scope and fails to address the broader ecological significance of lands designated for agricultural use. The cultural dimension of nature, particularly in relation to Indigenous and rural communities, is recognized in specific contexts, but it remains peripheral to the main policy narrative. Overall, the PNDs demonstrate a clear prioritization of economic interests over environmental or cultural considerations, offering limited integration of nature's broader ecological and cultural roles within their framework.

3.2.1.2 Life Frames Framework

Applying the **Life Frames Framework (LFF)** to the analysis of biodiversity and agricultural public policy instruments reveals important patterns in how these policies prioritize particular values of nature based on their underlying conceptualizations of human–nature relationships. Each "life frame" reflects a distinct way of relating to nature, and analysing policy through this lens highlights which relational approaches are favoured or neglected in official discourse.

The analysis shows³ that the majority of the policies reviewed align with the '**living from**' frame, which centres on the instrumental value of nature, emphasizing its role in providing tangible resources necessary for sustaining livelihoods. A smaller number are characterized by the '**living in**' frame. This frame recognizes nature as an integral part of people's daily lives, cultural identities, and social practices. It highlights the way in which the environment is seen not merely as a resource but as an essential setting that nurtures human well-being, traditions, and social cohesion. An even smaller group reflect the '**living with**' frame, acknowledging nature's intrinsic value and highlighting the importance of protecting life-supporting ecological systems, as well as recognizing moral obligations toward other-than-human beings.

Significantly, none of the policies analysed embody the '**living as**' frame, which expresses a profound sense of oneness, kinship, and interdependence with nature, typically found in Indigenous and other ontologies. This result is particularly noteworthy. While the NFF succeeds in recognizing the cultural dimensions of the human–nature relationship, it tends to conceptualize humans and nature

³ See Annex 2 for the completed Life Futures Framework table with the corresponding policies

as separate entities that interact with each other. It does not fully capture **relational ontologies**—common among many Indigenous Peoples—which reject the separation of humans and nature, envisioning instead living assemblages that are dynamically interconnected and often having sacred dimensions. These relational ontologies are more accurately represented in the LFF's concept of **'living as'** nature, where the rigid boundary between society and nature collapses. The absence of 'living as' perspectives in the policies analyzed suggests that current policy frameworks have yet to fully integrate these more holistic and relational approaches to human–nature interconnection.

This broader understanding frames the detailed analysis of individual policy instruments. The **National Policy for the Integrated Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services**, developed by the Ministry of the Environment, predominantly reflects the living from perspective. Throughout this policy, nature is presented as essential to societal well-being and national development, emphasizing its role as the foundation for providing ecosystem services critical to human prosperity. The policy explicitly states: *"It acknowledges the strategic importance of biodiversity as the primary source, foundation, and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that support the country's development, underpin its competitiveness, and are fundamental to the well-being of Colombian society."* While the living from perspective dominates, the policy also integrates elements of the living in perspective in specific instances. It recognizes the complex relationship between people and their environments, stating: *"Territories are understood as adaptive, resilient, and complex socio-ecosystems with their own structure and functioning. These systems provide ecosystem services and shape the cultural context(s) that develop within them"*.

However, there is also a notable, albeit isolated, reference that aligns with the **'living with'** frame, when the policy asserts: *"Life is the ultimate value. The survival of life on the planet depends on the protection of both the tangible and intangible components of biodiversity, as well as an understanding of its dynamic nature."* Here, the policy acknowledges the intrinsic value of life itself, recognizing the importance of biodiversity protection not solely for human benefit but for the continued existence of life on Earth. This suggests an underlying, if limited, commitment to valuing biodiversity beyond its instrumental utility.

The **National Development Plans (NDPs)** primarily embody the **'living from'** frame, focusing on the instrumental role of nature as an economic asset to be utilized for livelihood improvement and national development. This orientation is evident in statements such as: *"To establish reserves on vacant lands, or lands that may later acquire this status, in order to implement a special regime of occupation, use, and allocation regulated by the National Government. This will allow the beneficiary to have land as an asset to initiate income-generating activities."* Here, land and nature are framed predominantly as resources for economic productivity. Nonetheless, elements of the **'living with'** frame are present in specific sections of the NDPs, particularly when discussing the conservation of fragile ecosystems. For example, the plans explicitly protect *páramos* by prohibiting disruptive activities: *"In areas designated as páramos, agricultural activities, exploration or exploitation of non-renewable natural resources, and the construction of hydrocarbon refineries are not permitted."* These instances reflect a recognition of the inherent value of critical ecosystems and the need for their preservation, even if such recognition remains relatively limited within the overall economic focus of the plans.

In conclusion, this application of the Life Frames Framework provides a deeper understanding of the values underpinning public policy on biodiversity and agricultural production. It highlights a predominant emphasis on divergences between relational ontologies and values and instrumental ontologies and values of nature, while revealing a significant gap in policy recognition of the deeper relational ontologies represented by the 'living as' frame. This insight points to a critical opportunity: for future policy development to consider the sustainability of these different life frames and to give more space to 'living as' human-nature.

3.2.2 Desk-based study of Government Investments

A review of Colombia's General Budget of the Nation (GNB) was conducted to identify which public policies have received the greatest emphasis in terms of financial resources. The GNB serves as the government's primary annual instrument for planning and documenting public expenditures. It outlines the allocation of funds to specific public policies and designates the ministries or agencies responsible for their execution. By analyzing the GNB, we gain valuable insights into the government's fiscal priorities and how resources are distributed across different sectors.

In Colombia, the two principal government bodies responsible for agriculture and biodiversity are the **Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development** and the **Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development**. The first one is tasked with formulating and coordinating policies related to agriculture, fisheries, forestry, and rural development. Its mandate involves promoting economic growth while aiming to ensure environmental sustainability in productive sectors. The second one oversees the design and implementation of strategies for environmental management, including land-use planning, environmental zoning, and the enforcement of regulations that support sustainable development and ecological protection.

Figure 3 presents the historical budget trends for these two ministries in the GNB. It reveals a steady but relatively limited allocation of resources to the Ministry of Environment, in contrast to the consistently higher funding received by the Ministry of Agriculture throughout the period analyzed. Although the agricultural budget saw a decline toward the end, it remained above that of the environmental sector. This budgetary disparity highlights the government's historical prioritization of agriculture and rural development over environmental protection, offering a clear reflection of broader national policy orientations.

Figure 3 Budget trends for Colombia Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development

In addition to the main entities responsible for formulating environmental and agricultural policies, there are other institutions that play a key role in these sectors and whose budgets were also reviewed. In the agricultural sector, the **Rural Development Agency (ADR)**, known before 2015 as INCODER, is in charge of structuring, co-financing, and implementing Comprehensive Agricultural and Rural Development Plans aimed at promoting sustainable development in rural areas of Colombia. In the environmental sector, the **National Natural Parks of Colombia** are responsible for managing the National Natural Parks System, overseeing protected areas, and coordinating the National Protected Areas System (SINAP) in order to conserve biodiversity and promote the

sustainable use of natural resources. Meanwhile, the **National Environmental Fund (FONAM)** operates as a special account management system under the Ministry of the Environment and provides funding for activities, studies, research, plans, programs, and projects aimed at strengthening environmental management and promoting the protection, conservation, improvement, and restoration of the environment (Table 7).

Table 7 Main Colombian policies and total budgets allocated

		Agricultural sector		Environmental sector		
		Ministry of Agriculture	ADR	Ministry of Environment	FONAM	National Natural Parks
Policy with budgetary priority	Policy	Agro Ingreso Seguro	Analysis, design, and construction of National Irrigation Drainage districts	Administration of the Environmental Compensation Fund for Investment Projects	Implementation of National Environmental Policies	Administration, Conservation, and Management of the National Parks System
	Total amount (2020 Eur millions)	332.033	95.778	29.672	95.215	58.706
	Total Years	3	5	4	3	9
Policy with continuity priority	Policy	Rural Housing Subsidy for Displaced Populations	Implementation of the National Rural Development Project	National Water Policy	Administration of Resources for the Evaluation and Monitoring of Environmental Licenses	
	Total amount (2020 Eur millions)	245.592	68.726	14.023	80.543	
	Total Years	7	5	9	7	

Within the Ministry of Agriculture, the policy that received the highest priority in terms of resource allocation—along with being the one with the largest budget among all the policies analyzed—was Agro Ingreso Seguro. This program was designed with the overarching goal of enhancing the productivity and competitiveness of agricultural production in Colombia. It aimed to strengthen the country's integration into international markets, thereby fostering growth in the agricultural sector and contributing to the reduction of rural poverty. The policy was structured around two main components: Support for Competitiveness (APC) and Sectoral Economic Support (APS). The first component focused on preparing the agricultural sector to face increased exposure to international competition, particularly as a result of free trade agreements. It aimed to equip producers with the tools and resources necessary to improve their productivity and adapt to the challenges of global market integration. The second component was intended to protect the incomes of producers during the transitional phase. During this period, it was expected that producers would gradually improve their efficiency and competitiveness, thereby becoming more resilient to market fluctuations. However, the implementation of Agro Ingreso Seguro was marred by serious issues. Investigations revealed multiple instances of corruption, including the improper allocation of benefits to wealthy landowning families. There was a lack of adequate oversight and monitoring, which led to the misuse of public funds and the unjustified expansion of financial resources allocated to the program.

The policy with the longest continuity within the Ministry of Agriculture was the Rural Housing Subsidy for Displaced Populations. This program focused on both the construction of new housing units and the improvement of existing homes in rural areas. Its central goal was to guarantee access to dignified and safe housing for families who had been forcibly displaced due to violence or conflict, prioritizing their specific needs and vulnerabilities. By targeting rural displaced populations, the policy aimed to address not only immediate housing deficits but also to contribute to long-term social stability and inclusion. Adequate housing was considered a foundational element in the process of reintegration and restitution of rights for displaced communities. The initiative was particularly significant in post-conflict contexts, where rebuilding rural territories and restoring the dignity of affected populations was a national priority (Departamento Nacional de Planeación [DNP], n.d.).

With regard to the Rural Development Agency (ADR), the policy that received the most funding was the Analysis, Design, and Construction of National Irrigation and Drainage Districts. This initiative involves capturing water from surface or underground sources and distributing it through a network of conveyance and distribution systems to agricultural plots, where farming and livestock production activities are carried out. The primary goal is to reduce the risk of losses due to droughts or floods by ensuring a stable and managed water supply. It also encompasses the provision of specialized equipment, and the design of programs aimed at the modernization, rehabilitation, and ongoing maintenance of these infrastructure systems within their areas of influence. This policy plays a critical role in increasing agricultural productivity, stabilizing rural livelihoods, and promoting sustainable land use in Colombia's countryside (*Agencia de Desarrollo Rural*, n. d.).

In turn, the longest-running policy within the Rural Development Agency (ADR) was the Implementation of the National Rural Development Project. This policy encompasses time-bound initiatives that make partial use of public resources with the objective of creating, expanding, improving, or restoring the capacity for production or service provision by the State in rural areas. These projects are specifically designed to stimulate income generation and increase productivity among small and medium size producers. By doing so, they aim to improve the living conditions of rural communities while simultaneously enhancing national competitiveness. The approach recognizes that sustainable rural development is closely tied to the economic empowerment of local populations and the strengthening of territorial capacities for development (*Agencia de Desarrollo Rural*, n. d.).

Within the Ministry of Environment, the policy that received the highest level of funding was the **Administration of the Environmental Compensation Fund for Investment Projects**. This fund functions as a financial redistribution mechanism aimed at promoting a more equitable allocation of resources among the country's **Regional Autonomous Corporations (CARs)**—decentralized public entities responsible for environmental management within their respective regions. Their key functions include environmental planning and oversight, the conservation of natural resources such as water, soil, flora, and fauna, and the promotion of sustainable development practices that balance environmental protection with economic and social progress. The fund primarily benefits the fifteen CARs with the smallest approved budgets, including the seven **Sustainable Development Corporations**, in an effort to reduce regional disparities and bolster the institutional capacity of those with limited financial means. The resources allocated through the fund may be used to support operating costs, investment projects, and debt servicing commitments. (Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, n.d.)

The longest-running policy under the Ministry of Environment is the National Water Policy, established in 2010. This policy outlines a comprehensive framework for the integrated management of water resources over a twelve-year period. It was developed in response to increasing concerns over water availability, quality, and governance, and seeks to provide unified national guidelines for addressing the country's water-related challenges. The policy emphasizes the efficient, equitable, and sustainable use of water, recognizing it as a strategic resource vital to Colombia's social, economic, environmental, and cultural development. It highlights the need to

preserve water resources not only to meet current demands but also to ensure their availability for future generations. Importantly, the National Water Policy is designed to work in coordination with other major environmental policies, particularly the National Biodiversity Policy. This alignment reinforces the policy's objective of promoting the conservation and sustainable use of Colombia's natural resources and biodiversity, reflecting a holistic approach to environmental governance and ecosystem protection (*Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, 2025*).

The policy that received the most funding from the National Environmental Fund (FONAM) was the Implementation of National Environmental Policies Contributing to the Sectoral Goals of the National Development Plan (PND). This initiative plays a role in advancing Colombia's environmental agenda and achieving the sustainability objectives outlined in the country's long-term planning strategy. The primary aim of this policy is to support the effective implementation of national environmental strategies that align with the sectoral targets of the PND. These policies cover a wide range of critical environmental areas, including natural resource management, climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation, and the promotion of a circular economy. By addressing these areas, the policy contributes not only to environmental protection but also to the broader goals of sustainable development and resilience in the face of ecological challenges (*Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, n.d.*).

As a national financing instrument, FONAM serves a role in the execution of environmental programs and projects. It provides financial support for initiatives implemented at the national, regional, and local levels, ensuring that environmental policies are not only designed but also operationalized effectively across territories. The fund thus acts as a bridge between national policy frameworks and local environmental action, reinforcing Colombia's commitment to sustainable development and the well-being of its ecosystems and communities (*Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, n.d.*). In line with this mission, the policy with the longest duration under FONAM was the Administration of Resources for the Evaluation and Monitoring of Environmental Licenses. This policy focused on ensuring oversight and compliance in the licensing process, thereby strengthening environmental governance and supporting the sustainable use of natural resources over time.

Regarding National Natural Parks of Colombia (*Parques Nacionales Naturales de Colombia - PNN*), the policy that was both the most heavily prioritized in terms of funding and had the longest duration was the Administration, Conservation, and Management of the National Parks System. This policy embodies the core mission of the institution itself: to oversee and manage the country's protected areas and to coordinate the National System of Protected Areas (*SINAP*). Through the implementation of this long-standing policy, the entity ensures ecological integrity, supports scientific research, fosters environmental education, and strengthens local community engagement in conservation efforts.

In conclusion, the review of Colombia's policy priorities clearly shows a greater emphasis on agricultural development compared to environmental initiatives. Within the Ministry of Agriculture and the Rural Development Agency, significant resources and long-term commitments were directed toward boosting agricultural productivity -such as *Agro Ingreso Seguro-*, improving rural infrastructure, and supporting displaced populations. In contrast, although environmental policies received important support through mechanisms like the Environmental Compensation Fund and the National Water Policy, they generally played a secondary role in terms of resource allocation and institutional focus. This contrast highlights the government's strategic prioritization of agricultural growth and rural development as drivers of economic progress, while environmental management, though recognized as essential, remained a complementary rather than a central objective in national policy implementation.

3.2.3 Stakeholder Interviews

Among government officials, Sandra Vilardy, former Vice Minister of Environmental Policy at the Ministry of Environment, was interviewed. From the research community, Guillermo Rudas, a member of the Advisory Committee of Experts at the National Environmental Forum, was also interviewed. Additionally, representatives from the Agricultural Sector Financing Fund (FINAGRO) were consulted. FINAGRO is a national mixed-economy entity operating as a credit institution linked to the Ministry of Agriculture. It provides funding under favorable conditions to financial institutions, which in turn offer credit for productive projects. To further facilitate access to financing, FINAGRO also manages instruments that support the development of agricultural projects. Interviews were conducted with Ana María Yaruro, advisor on agricultural finance and risk policy; Camilo Quesada, presidential advisor; and Juan Pablo Bustamante, Vice President of Investments.

Thematic analysis reveals a persistent lack of an integrated policy framework that bridges biodiversity and the agricultural sector. Interviewees widely agree that these two areas have historically been approached in isolation. As one environmental economist emphasized, "an integrated policy has not been developed; it is the great absentee." A biodiversity specialist attributed this gap to a longstanding perception of rurality, marked by an imbalance between agricultural activities and biodiversity considerations. They explained that "rurality is seen as linked to agriculture, but the other elements of rurality—like biodiversity—are ignored. There's a cultural imaginary around rural land: taming it for productivity." This disjointed view has translated into a century of agricultural policy development, while biodiversity has only recently started receiving attention, with comparatively weaker institutional support. The absence of a unified approach continues to shape fragmented public policies.

The prioritization of agricultural productivity over biodiversity is clearly illustrated in the case of the 'Agro Ingreso Seguro' program. According to rural finance experts and agricultural policy advisors, this program has been one of the most significant agricultural policies of the past 15 years due to its longevity and substantial funding. They explained that it was designed to enhance rural productivity, focusing on the mechanization of agriculture and the long-term competitiveness of the sector through infrastructure investments such as irrigation systems. However, the program largely neglected environmental factors and excluded smallholder farmers, promoting a model of productivity reminiscent of the American agroindustrial paradigm. This policy trajectory underscores a systemic preference for agricultural modernization at the expense of ecological sustainability.

In contrast, biodiversity protection policies are valued for their symbolic and regulatory impact, despite practical limitations. An environmental specialist emphasized the importance of instruments such as protected areas, collective territories, forest reserves, and the designation of strategic ecosystems. These measures have helped curb biodiversity loss by formally restricting land transformation, often deterring private investment. "Even if they're just on paper, they have slowed down private sector encroachment," the expert noted. However, they also acknowledged that these instruments can lead to governance challenges and social conflict, particularly when certain stakeholders are excluded from decision-making processes. Thus, while symbolically powerful, these policies highlight ongoing tensions between conservation objectives and the need for social inclusion.

Stakeholders from rural finance institutions expressed differing yet overlapping visions for the future of rural and environmental policy. According to them, current rural financial instruments are largely reactive, often encouraging suboptimal decisions based on short-term returns, such as planting oil palm. They argued for a reoriented insurance mechanism that promotes context-specific, sustainable practices rather than a uniform approach. The emphasis, they suggested, should shift from merely facilitating sectoral entry to addressing the risks and consequences associated with participation. Their vision largely aligns with the *living from* frame, which emphasizes the instrumental value of nature in sustaining livelihoods, but also incorporates

elements of the *living in* frame, recognizing the relational and cultural significance of the natural environment. This blended perspective points toward a more contextually grounded and inclusive approach to rural policy.

A strategic reimagining of biodiversity is seen as essential for future policymaking, moving beyond an exclusively aesthetic appreciation. A biodiversity policy advocate urged a shift from seeing biodiversity as merely beautiful or symbolic, toward recognizing it as a strategic asset for economic growth and climate resilience. "We must shift from the aesthetic to the functional—to recover lost nature in a way that supports the economy and builds resilience to climate change," they stated. Similarly, a sustainability economist called for a coordinated approach between agricultural and environmental policies, emphasizing regenerative food systems and ecological restoration as central pillars for future development. Together, these perspectives envision a future in which biodiversity and agriculture are no longer positioned as opposing forces, but as mutually reinforcing elements. Conceptually, this vision blends the *living from* and *living with* frames, acknowledging both the instrumental value of biodiversity for human prosperity and the moral and ecological imperatives of preserving the life-supporting systems of the planet.

3.2.4 Discussion

The discourse analysis through the lens of the Nature Futures Framework shows that the dominant orientation of public policies aligns strongly with the Nature for Society perspective, where nature is primarily valued for the ecosystem services and economic benefits it provides to humans. Nature is framed predominantly as an external resource and seen as an economic asset, valued for the ecosystem services and material benefits it provides to human well-being and national development. Biodiversity is framed functionally, supporting agricultural productivity, without recognition of its agency or relational value. Land is portrayed chiefly as a productive resource, reinforcing a narrow utilitarian logic that neglects ecological integrity and deeper relational connections with nature.

The LFF analysis further nuances these findings. While most policies align with the 'living in' frame—acknowledging nature as foundational to social well-being and livelihoods—a significant portion also reflects the 'living from' frame, underlining the economic exploitation of nature. Only a few policies exhibit a 'living with' frame, recognizing intrinsic ecological values and moral obligations toward non-human beings. Notably, none of the policies embody the 'living as' frame, which envisions a profound interdependence and kinship with nature, common in Indigenous and cosmocentric worldviews.

This result is particularly noteworthy because it underscores the complementary value of the Life Frames Framework when used alongside the Nature Futures Framework (NFF). While the NFF succeeds in recognizing cultural dimensions of the human–nature relationship, it tends to conceptualize humans and nature as separate entities that interact with each other. It does not fully capture relational ontologies—common among many Indigenous Peoples—which reject the separation of humans and nature, envisioning instead living assemblages that are dynamically interconnected and often carry sacred dimensions. These relational worldviews are more accurately represented in the LFF's concept of 'living as' nature, where the rigid boundary between society and nature collapses. The absence of 'living as' perspectives in the policies analyzed suggests that current policy frameworks have yet to fully integrate these more holistic and relational approaches to human–nature interconnection.

The empirical findings reflect these theoretical tensions. Current public policies in Colombia continue to be shaped by a colonial-modernity imaginary that views rural land primarily as a territory to be "tamed" and made productive. Environmental concerns are often subordinated to agricultural expansion and economic growth. Biodiversity is considered valuable mainly insofar as it supports productivity, while policies that might recognize the intrinsic or relational value of nature remain rare and weakly institutionalized. These dynamics resonate with broader critiques found in

recent literature. For example, as discussed by Stirling et al. (2024) and others, the dominance of control-oriented imaginaries—grounded in colonial views of nature as a passive object for human domination—continues to structure policy and governance. Calls for paradigm shifts are important but insufficient; what is needed is a transformation at the level of dominant relational formations, moving from control to care.

Further, reflections from the literature (e.g., Büscher et al., 2023) highlight how conservation practices often impose a narrow, exclusionary vision of "pristine" landscapes, erasing Indigenous and local histories of cohabitation with nature. This critique is highly relevant to the current analysis. Policies that instrumentalize biodiversity or seek to "protect" it without acknowledging diverse ontologies risk marginalizing local communities, exacerbating social injustices, and undermining the very conservation goals they seek to achieve. A pluralistic conceptualization of biodiversity, one that recognizes multiple ways of relating to and valuing the living world, is necessary to build more inclusive, legitimate, and effective policy frameworks.

In conclusion, the analysis shows that although there is a growing recognition of the importance of biodiversity in policy discourse, the dominant frameworks remain deeply entrenched in instrumental and anthropocentric logics. Real transformation will require moving beyond surface-level integration of cultural dimensions, towards a more fundamental rethinking of the human–nature relationship. The complementary use of the NFF and LFF provides powerful tools to expose these limitations and suggest new pathways forward: pathways grounded not just in ecosystem service provision, but in relationality, care, justice, and interdependence.

3.3 Kenya

3.3.1 Discourse analysis

Kenya's principal policy frameworks relevant to this study are **Kenya Vision 2030**, the **National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) 2000**, the **Draft NBSAP 2019–2030**, the **Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS) 2010–2020**, and the **Agriculture Policy 2021**. Each of these frameworks was selected for its strategic relevance to the intersections of agriculture, biodiversity, and sustainable development. **Kenya Vision 2030** provides the country's overarching development blueprint, outlining the long-term goals for economic transformation, social equity, and environmental sustainability. The **NBSAP 2000** and the **Draft NBSAP 2019–2030** were included for their central role in guiding biodiversity conservation and aligning national priorities with the Convention on Biological Diversity. The **ASDS 2010–2020** was reviewed because it set the agenda for agricultural modernization and growth during the study period, directly influencing land use, rural livelihoods, and ecosystem integrity. Similarly, the **Agriculture Policy 2021** was incorporated to capture the latest policy directions toward sustainable and climate-smart agriculture. These frameworks collectively define Kenya's policy stance on the interlinkages between agriculture, biodiversity, and rural development.

3.3.1.1 Nature Futures Framework

Kenya's long-term development blueprint, **Vision 2030**, seeks to transform the country into a "newly industrializing, middle-income nation providing a high quality of life in a clean and secure environment" (GoK, 2007). It is envisioned to be based upon economic, social and political pillars supported by strong macroeconomic stability, infrastructure, land reform, governance reforms, science and innovation, and environmental stewardship.

Vision 2030's Environmental Pillar its commitment to conservation and restoration of natural resources. The Vision *"the goal for the environmental sector is to be a nation living in a clean, secure, and sustainable environment"* and seeks to *"increase forest cover to at least 10% of total land area, conserve wildlife resources, and promote sustainable management of water catchment areas."* This demonstrates Kenya's alignment with the NFF's call to uphold nature's inherent worth

by safeguarding ecosystems that support both ecological balance and the nation's long-term resilience.

Vision 2030's Economic Pillar embodies by recognizing natural resources as engines of economic growth and social progress. The Vision emphasizes that *"the economic pillar aims to achieve and sustain an average economic growth rate of 10% per annum,"* a goal to be achieved through sectors such as agriculture, tourism, and energy. It further underscores that *"sustainable management of land, water, and biodiversity resources is critical for the realization of the Vision's economic goals."* These strategies reflect how nature's provisioning services, fertile soils, clean water, forests, and scenic landscapes, are directly tied to Kenya's prosperity, productivity, and employment creation, . Kenya Vision 2030's Social Pillar *"the preservation of cultural heritage and traditional knowledge systems that enhance environmental stewardship."* This acknowledges the deep spiritual and cultural relationships many Kenyan Indigenous communities, such as the Ogiek, Maasai, and Mijikenda, maintain with their natural landscapes. These connections are central to their sense of belonging, morality, and collective identity, mirroring the NFF's recognition of nature as an inseparable part of human culture and life.

both seek to balance ecological integrity, human prosperity, and cultural harmony. Vision 2030 operationalizes the ideals of the NFF by embedding conservation ethics, sustainable use of natural resources, and respect for cultural values within its three foundational pillars of Environmental, Economic, and Social, offering a holistic roadmap for a sustainable and inclusive future.

Applying the **ASDS 2010–2020** largely instrumental, viewing conservation as a way to sustain agricultural yields rather than as a moral or ecological imperative, weakening the Nature for Nature perspective. This reflected the global development discourse of the early 2010s, where ecological sustainability was acknowledged but primarily framed as a means to achieve human-centered objectives.

The Nature for Society perspective was the dominant framing of the ASDS (2010–2020). The strategy placed strong emphasis on increasing agricultural productivity, competitiveness, and profitability as pathways to food security and poverty reduction. It prioritized commercialization of smallholder agriculture and the development of agribusiness and value chains to stimulate market-oriented growth. Furthermore, the ASDS promoted expanding irrigation infrastructure, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, and improving access to quality farm inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, and credit. Complementary efforts focused on reducing post-harvest losses, strengthening market linkages, and enhancing food security and job creation. The ASDS strategy was rooted in Kenya's Vision 2030 agenda, which positioned agriculture as a key driver of economic development and social welfare. The ASDS thus conceptualized nature primarily as a resource base whose productive use could alleviate poverty and promote national prosperity. This utilitarian orientation reflected a "Nature for Society" worldview, emphasizing efficiency, productivity, and technological advancement. While it succeeded in mobilizing investment and institutional reform, it also entrenched a productionist paradigm that treated ecological systems as instruments for growth, with limited attention to their long-term regenerative capacities.

The ASDS was largely social and developmental and it was meant to enhance inclusivity, equity, and efficiency in agricultural delivery systems. Yet, while these measures acknowledged the value of community participation, they did not fully embrace the cultural and spiritual relationships that many Kenyan communities maintain with land, water, and nature. The ASDS treated inclusion as a means to increase productivity and governance effectiveness rather than as a recognition of biocultural diversity or relational ethics. Thus, the Nature as Culture frame was weakly represented, overshadowed by economic modernization goals. Its limited integration reflected a gap in policy recognition of Indigenous and place-based relationships with the environment.

In summary, the ASDS (2010–2020) was fundamentally a "Nature for Society" policy, emphasizing agriculture as a tool for economic growth, food security, and poverty alleviation. The Nature for

Nature perspective was only partially acknowledged through environmental conservation and climate adaptation strategies, which were justified as means to sustain productivity. The Nature as Culture dimension appeared marginally, visible in participatory and gender-sensitive initiatives but lacking deeper engagement with cultural and ecological worldviews. To move toward the vision proposed by NFF, future policies must balance all three perspectives. This means complementing economic growth with stronger ecological integrity and deeper recognition of cultural values and Indigenous stewardship, ensuring agriculture evolves as a system that sustains both human prosperity and the living planet.

Thus, while the policy acknowledges the need to protect the natural base, it does so mainly to secure future yields and reduce vulnerability to climate shocks. This signals a moderate alignment with the Nature for Nature perspective, where conservation is valued, but mostly as a means to sustain production rather than an end in itself.

The Nature for Society perspective is the dominant framing of the Agriculture Policy (2021). The policy strongly emphasizes increasing productivity, competitiveness, and profitability across all subsectors of agriculture. Key strategies include enhancing access to quality seeds, fertilizers, and credit; modernizing agricultural technology and mechanization; expanding irrigation infrastructure to improve water use efficiency; and promoting commercialization and value addition along agricultural value chains. Other strategies focus on reducing post-harvest losses, strengthening market access and trade, and supporting agribusiness and agro-industrial development to create jobs and boost rural incomes. The policy views nature as productive capital to be managed efficiently for human benefit. This anthropocentric and utilitarian orientation reflects a strong “Nature for Society” perspective, positioning agriculture as the engine of Kenya’s socio-economic transformation. However, this also risks sidelining ecological limits and non-market values of nature in pursuit of growth.

The Nature as Culture perspective recognizes that sustainable agriculture depends not only on managing ecosystems but also on sustaining cultural practices, social relations, and Indigenous knowledge. The policy partially integrates this perspective through strategies that promote community participation, devolution of agricultural governance to county governments, and empowerment of women, youth, and marginalized groups in agricultural planning and decision-making. It also encourages community-based natural resource management and integration of local and traditional knowledge into extension and training systems. While these strategies create space for community voice and knowledge, they do not deeply engage with biocultural values or spiritual ties to land and landscape that characterize Kenya’s rural livelihoods. Hence, the policy acknowledges but underrepresents the Nature as Culture perspective, reflecting a developmental focus that values participation as a tool for efficiency rather than a recognition of cultural coexistence with nature.

The agricultural policy could move beyond utilitarian interpretations by integrating ecological ethics and cultural worldviews into agricultural planning. Doing so would strengthen its foundation for a resilient, just, and regenerative agricultural future, to one that values nature not only for what it provides but also for what it is and what it means to the communities who live with and within it.

From an NFF perspective, the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2000) reflect “Nature for Society,” emphasizing human well-being and economic development, and “Nature for Nature,” which upholds the intrinsic value of ecosystems. The dimension of “Nature as Culture” is also incorporated through the acknowledgment of Indigenous knowledge systems and cultural values as integral to biodiversity conservation; however, in both the 2000 and the Draft NBSAP 2019–2030 strategies, such recognition and its practical implementation remain limited in scope.

3.3.1.2 Life Futures Framework

The “*Living from Nature*” perspective emphasizes the material and economic benefits derived from ecosystems, is reflected in Vision 2030’s Economic Pillar, which commits to “*transforming*

agriculture from subsistence to an innovative, commercially oriented and modern sector” through the Agricultural Sector Transformation and Growth Strategy. This strategy promotes “*sustainable utilization of land, water and natural resources to achieve food security and economic growth,*” illustrating how livelihoods are drawn directly from nature. The “*Living in Nature*” perspective focuses on people’s cultural and spiritual relationships with nature, aligns with Vision 2030’s Social Pillar, which calls for “*preservation and promotion of national culture, traditional knowledge, and heritage*” under the Culture and Heritage Flagship Project implemented by the National Museums of Kenya. This reflects how communities such as the Ogiek and Maasai maintain identity and belonging through their interactions with natural landscapes.

The third perspective is on “*Living with Nature*” frame, which emphasizes coexistence and stewardship as articulated under the Environmental Management and Conservation Strategy, where Vision 2030 pledges to “*improve governance and management of the environment and natural resources*” through programmes like the Water Towers, Forestry and Wildlife Conservation and Restoration Programmes and National Climate Change Action Plan (NCCAP). These initiatives foster resilience and balanced use of ecosystems. Finally, the “*Living as Nature*” frame, which views humans as integral to nature is underrepresented and not clearly captured by Vision 2030. Vision 2030 integrates fundamental elements of the NFF and LFF, reflecting commitments to biodiversity conservation, sustainable resource use, and cultural heritage preservation. While the Vision recognizes the “*Nature as Culture*” perspective by valuing cultural heritage, traditional knowledge, and community-based conservation, it largely overlooks the “*Living as Nature*” perspective, which conceptualizes humans as integral components of ecological systems. Bridging this conceptual gap calls for future policy frameworks that transcend anthropocentric development paradigms and adopt more biocentric and eco-relational ethics, as embodied in indigenous environmental worldviews and the “*Living as Nature*” perspective, to achieve a truly inclusive and sustainable relationship between people and nature.

The Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS) 2010–2020 aimed to transform Kenya’s agriculture into a profitable, competitive, and sustainable sector.. While the ASDS recognized environmental and social considerations, its dominant orientation remained economic and productivist, reflecting a narrow understanding of sustainability. The “*living from nature*” frame is the most dominant in the ASDS. The ASDS emphasizes strategies such as the commercialization and modernization of smallholder agriculture, promotion of agribusiness and value chain integration, and investment in irrigation, fertilizer use, and mechanization to boost productivity. It also prioritizes market access and rural infrastructure development to enhance competitiveness and income generation. These strategies treat land, soil, water, and biodiversity as productive inputs to be managed for maximum output. These measures are rooted in economic growth and food security, illustrating a utilitarian view of nature that prioritizes resource extraction and productivity over ecological balance or cultural meaning.

Elements of the “*living with nature*” frame are visible in the ASDS through its environmental sustainability and climate resilience components. Strategies such as soil and water conservation, promotion of agroforestry, adoption of climate-smart agriculture, integrated pest management, and sustainable land-use planning reflect an awareness of ecological interdependence and the need for stewardship. These initiatives encourage coexistence with natural systems by mitigating degradation and adapting to climate change. However, they remain largely instrumental, while sustainability is promoted primarily to maintain production capacity and reduce vulnerability to environmental risks rather than as an ethical or cultural obligation to care for nature. Hence, while the “*living with nature*” frame is present, it functions as a support mechanism for productivity rather than an alternative worldview.

The “*living in nature*” frame, which associates nature with cultural belonging, spirituality, and community identity, is weakly represented in the ASDS. Some elements, such as community-driven development programs, gender and youth inclusion, and decentralized extension services, show limited recognition of the social and cultural dimensions of agriculture. The ASDS also mentions

land reform and improved land access, but primarily in terms of efficiency and equity rather than cultural continuity or ancestral ties. The strategy thus overlooks the deep relational and symbolic meanings of land that shape rural identity and collective stewardship in Kenya. By failing to engage with Indigenous knowledge systems, customary governance, and local cultural values, the ASDS risks alienating communities for whom farming is a way of life, not merely a source of income.

The “living as nature” frame, where humans and nature are understood as inseparable and co-constitutive, is entirely absent from the ASDS. The strategy is grounded in a modernist, anthropocentric paradigm that treats nature as an external system to be managed and optimized through technology and markets. There is no acknowledgment of Indigenous cosmologies or relational ontologies that perceive land, humans, and nonhumans as interconnected. This omission limits the ethical and philosophical depth of Kenya’s agricultural policy, precluding the integration of regenerative approaches based on reciprocity, harmony, and respect for life.

In general, the ASDS 2010–2020 privileges “living from nature,” partially incorporates “living with nature,” and marginalizes or excludes “living in” and “living as nature.” It is dominated by economic rationality, focusing on productivity and commercialization at the expense of cultural, ecological, and relational values.

The Kenya Agriculture Policy (2021) seeks to promote “a modern, commercially oriented, competitive and sustainable agricultural sector” to achieve food and nutrition security, poverty reduction, and economic growth. When analyzed through the Life Frames Framework, the policy reveals the underlying values shaping Kenya’s agricultural transformation agenda. While it advances sustainability discourse more strongly than the earlier ASDS 2010–2020, its overall orientation remains productivity and market-driven, prioritizing economic efficiency over relational or cultural dimensions of human–nature relations.

The “living from nature” frame is the most dominant in the Agricultural Policy (2021). The policy emphasizes increased productivity, commercialization of smallholder farming, value addition, mechanization, irrigation expansion, and *market access* as central strategies. It seeks to enhance competitiveness and wealth creation by treating natural resources, that is, land, soil, water, and biodiversity, as productive assets. These strategies are justified by the need to ensure food and nutrition security, economic growth, and employment creation. However, this utilitarian framing positions nature primarily as a source of material benefits and ecosystem services, reinforcing an extractive relationship rather than one of reciprocity or stewardship.

Elements of the “living with nature” frame appear through the policy’s emphasis on climate change adaptation and mitigation, soil and water conservation, promotion of climate-smart agriculture, and sustainable resource management. These strategies demonstrate awareness of ecological interdependence and the need for stewardship to sustain productivity. These measures lie in maintaining long-term agricultural viability and reducing vulnerability to climate shocks. Yet, ecological sustainability is still framed instrumentally, as a means to secure production, rather than as an ethical responsibility to coexist with ecosystems.

The “living in nature” frame, is weakly reflected in the policy. Some strategies, such as mainstreaming gender and youth, community participation in planning and implementation, and devolution of agricultural governance to counties, partially engage social inclusion. However, the policy fails to recognize land as a site of ancestral and cultural attachment or to incorporate Indigenous and local knowledge systems. This limited engagement lies in the policy’s modernist and technocratic focus, rather than a cultural landscape and way of life.

The “living as nature” frame is almost entirely absent from the Agricultural Policy (2021). The document does not articulate strategies that view humans and nature as inseparable or promote relational ontologies of coexistence. There is no explicit incorporation of Indigenous cosmologies or holistic ecological ethics that recognize human life as part of broader natural processes. It reflects a deeply anthropocentric orientation where agriculture is conceptualized as human-managed

production within nature, not as a co-evolutionary process embedded in living systems. The omission of this frame reveals a critical gap in ethical and ecological grounding, limiting the potential for regenerative and holistic approaches to agricultural transformation.

Viewed through the Life Futures Framework, The NBSAP 2000 reflects a “Living from Nature” perspective by emphasizing human dependence on biodiversity for subsistence, economic needs, and survival, framing natural resources primarily as vital sources of livelihood and national development. “As Kenya gears itself towards industrial development, the importance of its biological resources cannot be overemphasized. Whether in the provision of food, industrial inputs, pulpwood, firewood, construction materials, medicines, ecosystem functions, or aesthetics, the conservation.” “These resources form the basic source of livelihood for the country’s population especially in view of the fact that about 80% of the country’s population directly or indirectly relies on biodiversity for survival

The NBSAP 2019–2030 demonstrates greater alignment with the “Living with Nature” frame, emphasizing coexistence and shared stewardship between people and ecosystems. “By 2030, Kenya will have a highly valued, conserved, and sustainably utilized biodiversity contributing to the socio-economic well-being of the people of Kenya.” This shift reflects a move from the 2000 plan’s predominantly anthropocentric outlook toward a more integrated approach that values both human and ecological well-being. The 2019–2030 strategy underscores sustainable use, restoration, and community-based management as mechanisms to maintain biodiversity while supporting livelihoods. Its vision of biodiversity being “highly valued, conserved, and sustainably utilized” for Kenya’s socio-economic development illustrates progress toward a future where human prosperity and ecological integrity are interdependent. Nevertheless, despite incorporating coexistence and stewardship principles, the strategy’s operational focus remains largely anthropocentric, emphasizing biodiversity’s role in supporting human systems rather than fully embodying an ecocentric “Flourishing of Life” perspective. A detailed analysis is presented in the LFF tables (see appendices).

3.3.2 Desk-based study of government Investments

A review of Kenya’s national budget since 2010 provides clear insight into the government’s fiscal priorities and how resources have been allocated to different policy sectors. Kenya’s annual budget serves as the government’s primary planning and expenditure tool, showing how funds are distributed, and which ministries or agencies are tasked with implementation. By examining these figures, we gain an understanding of Kenya’s long-term policy orientation, particularly in agriculture and environmental management.

The Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development is responsible for policies on crop production, livestock, fisheries, and rural livelihoods, with a central mandate to enhance food security and drive economic transformation. On the other hand, the Ministry of Environment, Climate Change and Forestry is charged with biodiversity conservation, sustainable land-use planning, climate adaptation, and environmental governance.

Over the years, the Ministry of Environment’s name has varied, but its role has consistently focused on protecting ecosystems, water towers, wetlands, and biodiversity. Examination of budgetary allocations over a twelve-year period shows that funding for environmental protection has been inconsistent and generally low compared to other sectors. Allocations increased from 2009/10 Financial Year to 2012/13, declined steadily between 2013/14 and 2018/19, and registered a modest recovery in 2019/20 and 2020/21. Even at its peak, spending on environmental functions has always been rarely exceeded 133,000,000 Euros annually, representing approximately 1 percent of Kenya’s total national budget during the same period, which was around 8 billion Euros in 2013/14 (see Table 8). This sharp disparity reflects how environmental priorities remain undervalued relative to other development sectors.

Agriculture, by contrast, has consistently received much larger allocations, reflecting its central role in the economy. According to the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (2024), agriculture contributes 21.8 percent of GDP, and its funding has generally trended upward despite occasional cuts. For example, the sector's allocation rose from 154.6 million Euros in 2008/09 to 229 million Euros in 2009/10 (48 percent increase) to support irrigation and revive production following severe drought. More recently, agriculture received 345 million Euros in 2019/20 and 563.4 million Euros in 2024/25, roughly 2 to 3 percent of the national budget. Even after a reduction to about 315.9 million to 386.2 million Euros in 2025/26, agriculture remained far better funded than environmental protection. This reflects a consistent government focus on boosting food security and rural development over direct investment in biodiversity conservation.

Sector performance mirrors these funding priorities. Agricultural growth has fluctuated sharply over the past decade, largely driven by weather conditions rather than steady productivity gains. While these trends justify the government's continued high investment in agriculture, they also highlight how insufficient funding for environmental protection undermines long-term resilience. Sustainable land use, biodiversity conservation, and climate adaptation, which are vital to stabilizing agricultural performance, remain severely underfunded relative to their importance within Kenya's overall budget framework.

Table 8 Annual Budget allocation to agriculture and environment sectors, Kenya

Financial Year	Agriculture (Kshs)	Agriculture (Euro)	Environmental Protection (Kshs)	Environmental Protection (Euro)
2009/2010	34,533,580,000	229,146,876.4	5,603,100,000	37,179,257.49
2010/2011	44,250,100,000	293,620,649.6	5,695,570,000	37,792,840.32
2011/2012	44,616,520,000	296,052,022.2	9,971,460,000	66,165,422.51
2012/2013	52,167,660,000	346,157,459.9	23,717,400,000	157,376,331.20
2013/2014	50,003,650,000	331,798,215.1	20,951,610,000	139,023,987.30
2014/2015	52,606,280,000	349,067,914.1	17,234,460,000	114,358,913.10
2015/2016	54,758,100,000	363,346,272.5	18,104,970,000	120,135,164.70
2016/2017	49,270,150,000	326,931,090.5	11,303,880,000	75,006,668.66
2017/2018	52,516,930,000	348,475,034.0	11,332,530,000	75,196,775.16
2018/2019	58,184,680,000	386,083,275.3	7,336,730,000	48,682,724.53
2019/2020	59,750,520,000	396,473,375.1	19,655,200,000	130,421,684.80
2020/2021	106,223,180,000	704,841,777.0	13,408,870,000	88,974,287.52
2021/2022	64,445,100,000	427,624,166.4	9,139,470,000	60,644,769.58
2022/2023	79,733,510,000	529,070,103.9	7,196,640,000	47,753,160.15
2023/2024	124,175,520,000	823,964,168.4	15,559,490,000	103,244,683.30
2024/2025	81,954,410,000	543,806,841.2	-	-

Source: Economic Surveys – Kenya National Bureau of Statistics
Exchange Rate of 1 Euro = 150.70 Kenya Shillings

Table 9 Annual Budget Allocation agriculture and environment sectors, Kenya

Financial Year	Annual Budget (Euro)	Agriculture (Euro)	Percentage change (%)	Environmental Protection (Euro)	Percentage change (%)
2009/2010	5,125,414,731.3	229,146,876.4	-	37,179,257.49	-
2010/2011	6,084,936,960.8	293,620,649.6	28.18	37,792,840.32	1.65
2011/2012	7,690,112,806.9	296,052,022.2	0.83	66,165,422.51	75.06
2012/2013	10,086,264,100.9	346,157,459.9	16.91	157,376,331.20	137.70
2013/2014	10,882,548,108.8	331,798,215.1	-4.15	139,023,987.30	-11.64
2014/2015	10,723,291,307.2	349,067,914.1	5.22	114,358,913.10	-17.77
2015/2016	13,275,381,552.8	363,346,272.5	4.07	120,135,164.70	5.07
2016/2017	15,028,533,510.3	326,931,090.5	-10.06	75,006,668.66	-37.57
2017/2018	15,185,136,031.9	348,475,034.0	6.62	75,196,775.16	0.25
2018/2019	16,682,149,966.8	386,083,275.3	10.79	48,682,724.53	-35.23
2019/2020	16,964,830,789.6	396,473,375.1	2.70	130,421,684.80	167.72
2020/2021	18,331,121,433.3	704,841,777.0	77.72	88,974,287.52	-31.77
2021/2022	20,106,171,201.1	427,624,166.4	-39.32	60,644,769.58	-21.20
2022/2023	21,964,167,219.6	529,070,103.9	23.69	47,753,160.15	116.23
2023/2024	23,883,875,248.8	823,964,168.4	55.68	103,244,683.30	-
2024/2025	25,534,173,855.3	543,806,841.2	-34.01	-	-

Source: Economic Surveys – Kenya National Bureau of Statistics

Exchange Rate of 1 Euro = 150.70 Kenya Shillings

Average budget allocation for Agriculture (3.04%) and Environment (0.70%)

Over the last two decades, successive governments have rolled out ambitious agricultural initiatives to boost productivity and enhance national food security. Between 2009 and 2011, government increased allocation by 66.4 million Euros to implement, the Economic Stimulus Programme (2009/10) which prioritized irrigation expansion to reduce reliance on rain-fed agriculture and support the subsidized fertilizer programme which was reintroduced in 2007, sought to lower input costs, improve yields, and promote smallholder commercialization. Recently, in 2023, the subsidized fertilizer programme was expanded which saw government allocation for the ministry increase by 64 percent to 823 million Euros from 524.2 million Euros in 2022. Between 2017 and 2022 during the implementation of the Big Four Agenda, which explicitly elevated food and nutrition security as a national priority, reinforcing agriculture's centrality in Kenya's development agenda, government funding had a sturdy annual rise. Agriculture consistently attracted far larger shares, particularly under Vision 2030 flagship projects like the Galana-Kulalu Irrigation Scheme and later under the Big Four Agenda, where food security was positioned as a central pillar. These interventions have consistently received high-level political attention, significant fiscal outlays, and strong institutional support.

3.3.3 Stakeholder Interviews

The stakeholder interviews were undertaken to review the implementation and financing of key policies under Kenya's Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Environment, Climate Change, and Forestry between 2010 and 2025. Insights from senior ministry officials, policy experts from the Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA) and officials from Kenya Forest Service and National Environmental Management Authority provided grounded perspectives on institutional performance, inter-ministerial coordination, and the broader policy landscape.

Since 2010, the government's prioritization of agricultural investment has primarily sought to achieve food security and support livelihoods. Agricultural investments have largely focused on productivity and commercialization measures, including large-scale irrigation expansion and modernization programmes such as the National Irrigation Acceleration Programme and the Galana–Kulalu Food Security Project (National Irrigation Authority, 2024). These have been complemented by input-subsidy and e-voucher schemes, value-chain and agribusiness development, and infrastructure support for cold-chain and export markets, particularly for high-value crops such as tea, coffee, and horticulture, including cut flowers, fruits, and vegetables.

Such interventions have predominantly favoured commercial and export-oriented agriculture. Tea, coffee, and horticulture remain Kenya's top foreign-exchange earners and continue to attract substantial public and private investment in production and extension services. Meanwhile, smallholder farmers, estimated at 8.6 million individuals across 4.5 million households, continue to supply the bulk of domestic food and sustain rural livelihoods, contributing roughly three-quarters of total agricultural output (FAO, 2023). Consequently, between 2010 and 2024, Kenya's policy and investment landscape has been characterized by robust support for export-led growth, while ecological stewardship, essential for biodiversity conservation, watershed integrity, and climate resilience, remains underfunded. This imbalance threatens the long-term sustainability of both export and smallholder food systems (Central Bank of Kenya, 2024).

According to KIPPRA agricultural policy expert, the implementation of the Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS) achieved significant milestones during the first phase of the Agricultural Sector Development Support Programme (ASDSP I, 2012–2017). Approximately 89% of targeted value chain actors participated in local climate-risk planning, demonstrating strong inclusion of women and youth. Beneficiary outreach reached 94% of the intended target, covering 423,421 of 452,786 people, with 96% male, 93% female, and 84% youth participation. The policy expert highlighted several key achievements under the ASDS framework. Among the most notable were the adoption of targeted value chain technologies at a rate of 84%, and the active engagement of at least 89% of stakeholders, including women and youth. The consolidation of fragmented crop laws under the Crops Act (2013) led to the establishment of the Agriculture and Food Authority (AFA), which enhanced regulatory coherence and minimized overlapping mandates. The creation of the Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) further strengthened the national agricultural research system and aligned research priorities with sectoral needs.

The formation and capacity building of value chain groups across the country, as well as partnerships and credit guarantee arrangements with development partners such as USAID, helped attract financing for value chain enterprises. The implementation of a sector-wide approach through the Agricultural Sector Coordination Unit (ASCU), complemented by biennial stakeholder meetings, improved coordination among ministries and development partners during the initial years. This process informed the 2013–2017 Medium-Term Investment Plan (MTIP). Moreover, ASDS served as Kenya's blueprint for the Comprehensive African Agricultural Development Programme (CAADP), aligning national strategies with the Malabo and Maputo commitments and facilitating Kenya's participation in the CAADP Biennial Reviews.

Despite these successes, implementation was not without challenges. KIPPRA expert observed that the transition to a devolved system of governance posed significant obstacles. Devolution led to role ambiguity, capacity gaps, and the gradual decline of the ASCU model, which had previously been central to sector coordination. The resulting misalignment between national and county functions affected program delivery, policy execution, and agricultural extension services. The planned scale-up of extension, irrigation, and resilience investments was also constrained by limited funding, public agricultural spending remained below the CAADP target of 10%. Additionally, audits and reviews of flagship irrigation projects, such as the Galana-Kulalu scheme, revealed issues of cost overruns, governance weaknesses, and poor implementation, which curtailed expected contributions to food security. Recurrent droughts and price shocks further slowed agricultural growth, making it difficult to achieve the ASDS target of 7% annual growth.

According to the KIPPRA policy expert, external influence played a substantial and largely positive role in ASDS implementation. Kenya's signing of the CAADP Compact in July 2010 positioned ASDS as the national CAADP plan, anchoring it to continental targets such as 6% annual agricultural growth, 10% public agricultural expenditure, and regular performance reviews through the CAADP Biennial Review mechanism. Moreover, the Agricultural Sector Development Support Programme (ASDSP I) was co-financed by the Government of Kenya and the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (Sida) at a total cost of approximately 32.2 million Euros. The program incorporated cross-cutting donor priorities, including gender equality, youth empowerment, climate and natural resource management, monitoring and evaluation, and results-based management. These priorities were operationalized through the development of a Management Information System, inclusion metrics, and local climate-risk planning frameworks.

Donor emphasis on private-sector participation was reflected in the establishment of credit guarantee partnerships with USAID to expand access to value chain financing. Overall, ASDS implementation largely embraced donor-driven principles of inclusion, climate resilience, transparency, and coordination. According to KIPPRA expert, "the main source of friction was not donor conditionalities, but institutional disruptions brought about by devolution," which complicated coordination and delayed program delivery.

The implementation rate of Kenya's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) can best be described as moderate to high, though uneven across different sectors and targets. According to insights from stakeholder interviews with officials from the National Environment Management Authority, the Kenya Wildlife Service, and a policy expert from KIPPRA, progress has been commendable but fragmented. Overall, a significant number of the Aichi Biodiversity Targets, and the subsequent post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework targets, have seen active intervention. However, the rate of achieving full attainment of these objectives varies considerably, reflecting sectoral disparities and resource constraints.

In the environmental and wildlife sectors, implementation is relatively high. KWS official noted that the establishment and management of protected areas such as national parks and reserves, alongside species-specific conservation programs for endangered species like the Black Rhino and Sable Antelope, have been particularly successful. Additionally, initiatives to combat illegal wildlife trade have intensified, supported by enhanced surveillance and community-based enforcement. In the forestry sector, progress has also been notable. NEMA official noted the Kenya Water Towers Agency's work and the National Tree Cover Restoration Initiative, as key drivers of increased tree planting. Nevertheless, gains in forest cover are offset by persistent deforestation linked to agricultural expansion and charcoal production.

By contrast, cross-sectoral integration, the mainstreaming of biodiversity into agriculture, energy, tourism, and manufacturing, remains weak. KIPPRA policy expert emphasized that despite existing policy frameworks, progress has been slow and largely project-based rather than systemic. He indicated that, while Kenya has made substantial strides in biodiversity conservation, the rate of implementation has yet to fully reverse biodiversity loss at the national level, indicating a gap between action and desired ecological outcomes.

The interviews underscored several notable successes achieved under the NBSAP. One of the most prominent achievements is the expansion and strengthening of protected areas. KWS official confirmed the successful gazettement of new protected areas and the establishment of numerous community conservancies. These developments have expanded wildlife habitats and improved landscape connectivity. Currently, approximately 8% of Kenya's landmass is protected under the Kenya Wildlife Service, with ongoing ecosystem restoration projects in Mt. Kenya, the Aberdares, and the Mau Forest Complex, which are critical national water catchment areas.

Another significant success involves the recovery of endangered wildlife species. Through rigorous anti-poaching measures, advanced monitoring technologies, and community engagement, Kenya

has achieved zero rhino poaching incidents since 2020, alongside a steady growth in elephant populations. The use of digital tools such as e-Citizen for revenue collection, remote wildlife cameras, and collaring of endangered species has further enhanced conservation outcomes.

The role of community engagement was strongly emphasized by both NEMA and KWS officials as instrumental in driving positive change. Sustained national campaigns have boosted progress toward the constitutional 10% tree cover target, with millions of seedlings planted, particularly in degraded water towers like the Mau Forest. Legislative and institutional advancements, such as the enactment of the Wildlife Conservation and Management Act, the Forest Conservation and Management Act, and the Climate Change Act, have also provided a solid legal backbone for implementation. Furthermore, the growth of community conservancies has become a globally recognized model, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, where conservation efforts are integrated with sustainable livelihoods through tourism and carbon credit projects. The development of a robust biodiversity data and monitoring system, including the National Biodiversity Data Bank and real-time wildlife tracking via the Earth Ranger platform, has strengthened evidence-based management and policy interventions.

Despite these successes, NEMA, KWS, and KIPPRA officials identified several persistent challenges affecting NBSAP implementation. Foremost among these is insufficient and unpredictable funding, commonly referred to as the “biodiversity finance gap.” Government allocations often fall short, while donor funding tends to be project-specific and time-bound, limiting the sustainability of long-term conservation programs. Human-wildlife conflict has also intensified as human populations expand into wildlife habitats. KWS official reported increasing cases of crop destruction, livestock predation, and human fatalities, which in turn undermine community support for conservation initiatives. Similarly, land use change and habitat fragmentation, driven by agricultural expansion, urban sprawl, and infrastructure development, remain the leading causes of biodiversity loss.

The interviews further revealed that climate change has exacerbated ecological pressures, with prolonged droughts, irregular rainfall patterns, and extreme weather events threatening both wildlife and forest ecosystems. The weak mainstreaming of biodiversity across government sectors and limited inter-agency coordination were also highlighted. According to the KIPPRA policy expert, biodiversity considerations are still poorly integrated into agriculture, mining, and energy sectors due to conflicting policy priorities, limited technical capacity, and weak enforcement of environmental impact assessment regulations. In addition, illegal activities, such as unauthorized logging, charcoal production, and poaching for bushmeat and trophies, continue to pose significant threats to conservation efforts.

The interviews revealed that external influence plays a major role in shaping NBSAP implementation. This influence primarily manifests through financial support from international development partners, the Global Environment Facility, bilateral donors, and conservation-oriented NGOs. Kenya’s NBSAP also aligns with the Convention on Biological Diversity, whose global frameworks guide target-setting and progress reporting. However, donors often come with specific thematic interests, such as climate resilience, forest carbon, or iconic species conservation, that may not always align perfectly with national priorities. To address this, the officials explained that Kenya has adopted a deliberate strategy of alignment between donor requirements and national goals, as articulated in the NBSAP and Kenya Vision 2030. NEMA official highlighted ongoing efforts to integrate donor-funded projects into national implementation systems to enhance sustainability and government ownership. Where donor agendas are overly prescriptive, the government negotiates flexibility to safeguard national interests, and in rare instances, declines funding that could distort policy coherence.

Enhanced monitoring, evaluation, and reporting systems have also been developed to improve accountability. These systems ensure that donor-funded activities are not only reported as required for funding disbursements but also tracked within Kenya’s broader NBSAP framework. As noted by the KIPPRA policy expert, this integration strengthens institutional learning and helps align external

financing with domestic biodiversity priorities. It is known that, external influence remains a defining feature of biodiversity governance in Kenya, the country has developed robust mechanisms to harness donor support for national benefit. By aligning external priorities with domestic strategies, ensuring institutional coordination, and embedding accountability within existing monitoring frameworks, Kenya continues to advance biodiversity conservation while maintaining strong national ownership and policy coherence.

In summary, the interviews revealed that Kenya's agricultural and environmental policy landscape between 2010 and 2025 has been marked by ambitious planning but uneven implementation. While donor-supported initiatives have catalyzed significant programmes in irrigation, reforestation, and climate-smart agriculture, their sustainability remains uncertain without stronger domestic financing, institutional coordination, and accountability mechanisms. The dual focus on commercial agriculture and export growth, coupled with limited attention to ecological integrity and smallholder support, underscores the need for a more integrated policy approach that aligns economic productivity with environmental resilience. Strengthening the link between policy design, financing, and implementation will be crucial to achieving the objectives of Vision 2030 and ensuring that Kenya's agricultural transformation remains both inclusive and ecologically sustainable.

3.3.4 Discussion

Kenya's policy landscape demonstrates clear progress in aligning biodiversity conservation and agricultural transformation with global sustainability frameworks. Discourse analysis and frameworks collectively demonstrate that while biodiversity is consistently present in national planning, agriculture remains the central axis of Kenya's development agenda. Vision 2030, the NBSAPs (2000 and 2019–2030), and the Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (2010–2020) reveal an overarching focus on resource use for livelihoods ("Living from Nature" and "Nature for Society") and growing recognition of ecological stewardship ("Living in Nature" and "Nature for Nature"). However, cultural, spiritual, and indigenous knowledge dimensions ("Living as Nature" and "Nature as Culture") remain underrepresented in policy implementation.

Financial review highlights persistent underinvestment in environmental protection relative to agriculture, despite biodiversity's foundational role in supporting food security, rural livelihoods, and climate resilience. While agriculture consistently receives between 2 and 3 percent of the national budget, allocations for environmental protection rarely exceed 0.3 percent. This imbalance undermines Kenya's ability to sustain agricultural productivity, address climate change impacts, and protect critical ecosystems in the long term. Without deliberate integration of cultural values, equitable benefit-sharing, and increased funding for biodiversity programs, Kenya risks achieving short-term agricultural gains at the expense of long-term ecological stability.

In parallel, biodiversity conservation and environmental management have been administered under the Ministry of Environment, whose nomenclature has varied over time. Despite its critical role, all of which underpin agricultural and economic stability, budgetary allocations for environmental protection over the past twelve years reveal marked inconsistency. Funding rose between 2009/10 and 2012/13, driven by forestry, wildlife conservation, climate initiatives, and UN Environment-supported resilience and restoration projects. Later, alignment with the Paris Agreement (2015), the National Climate Change Action Plan, and the Presidential 15 billion National Tree Planting Initiative by 2032 further attracted resources.

Generally, environmental allocations have remained project-driven and vulnerable to shifting government priorities. Declines during 2015/16–2018/19, and again in 2021/22 and 2022/23, reflected fiscal constraints from high debt servicing and the diversion of funds toward subsidies, healthcare, and COVID-19 economic recovery. Several environmental programmes stalled or received minimal disbursements as a result. Even at its peak, spending on environmental functions has been relatively

low and this is replicated in budgetary allocations at the county governments level where funding is not prioritized.

3.3.5 Recommendations

Policy implementation in the global south is an uphill task, however, achieving the country's sustainable development goals will require strengthen inter-sectoral coordination, inclusive governance and increased investment in sustainable agricultural practices. The framework and discourse provide complementary lenses for guiding Kenya's agricultural and biodiversity sectors toward sustainability. They emphasize resource use, ecosystem services, coexistence, and cultural identity. Together, these frameworks help align agricultural productivity goals with ecosystem stewardship, ensuring that development strategies support livelihoods while conserving biodiversity and integrating community knowledge, values, and resilience.

For meaningful progress, policies must move beyond rhetorical integration towards institutional coherence, where agriculture and biodiversity are managed not as parallel agendas but as interdependent systems.

To achieve this, several strategic shifts are necessary:

1. **Increase funding for biodiversity and environmental programs:** Increase budget funding to the Ministry of Environment, Climate Change and Forestry, ensuring that biodiversity conservation and climate adaptation receive proportional investment comparable to agriculture.
2. **Mainstream biodiversity into agricultural financing and planning:** Link agricultural subsidies, irrigation programs, and rural development initiatives to ecosystem restoration, soil health, and water conservation to stabilize agricultural productivity.
3. **Strengthen community participation and benefit-sharing mechanisms:** Enact into law the Benefit Sharing Bill and fully operationalize constitutional provisions for participatory land-use planning, community forest associations, and wildlife conservancies to ensure that local communities are co-owners of biodiversity resources.
4. **Integrate cultural and indigenous knowledge into policy implementation:** Expand "Living as Nature" and "Nature as Culture" perspectives by recognizing sacred landscapes, supporting indigenous seed systems, and embedding traditional ecological knowledge into conservation policies.
5. **Enhance monitoring, research, and policy coherence:** Improve data systems for tracking ecosystem health, agricultural biodiversity, and budgetary performance, while harmonizing biodiversity, agriculture, and climate policies to avoid conflicting mandates.
6. **Develop long-term resilience strategies:** Prioritize climate-smart agriculture, landscape restoration and biodiversity corridors as national resilience assets rather than peripheral programs, ensuring their inclusion in future Vision updates and sector plans.

4. Discussion

The comparative analysis of Cameroon, Kenya, and Colombia reveals a shared struggle to reconcile agricultural development with biodiversity conservation, despite notable differences in institutional capacity, historical trajectories, and sociocultural contexts. Across all three countries, policy discourse shows increasing recognition of biodiversity's importance for national development. Yet, in practice, agriculture remains the dominant policy and investment priority, resulting in structural imbalances that limit transformative progress toward sustainability.

A first common pattern is the predominance of instrumental and utilitarian framings of nature. In Kenya and Cameroon, policies overwhelmingly emphasize biodiversity as an asset for agricultural productivity, climate resilience, and rural livelihoods. Colombia demonstrates an even stronger alignment with "Nature for Society" and "living from" perspectives, where nature is framed primarily as an external resource that supports economic development. Although all three countries formally acknowledge ecological stewardship, intrinsic ecological values and relational perspectives remain weakly embedded in policy implementation. The absence or marginal presence of "living as" frames in all three contexts indicates that Indigenous and cultural ontologies, despite rhetorical recognition, have yet to fundamentally reshape policy design or execution.

Second, the findings reveal structural mismatches between policy ambitions and resource allocation. All three countries exhibit systematic underinvestment in biodiversity-related ministries and programs. In Kenya, environmental allocations rarely exceed 0.3 percent of the national budget, significantly lower than spending on agriculture. Cameroon shows a similar trend, with agricultural sectors consistently receiving higher allocations than biodiversity or forestry institutions. In Colombia, policies reflect a prioritization of agricultural expansion over ecological protection. These financial imbalances reinforce a predominantly utilitarian approach to nature and constrain the development of integrated socio-ecological strategies.

Third, all three countries exhibit institutional fragmentation that limits effective coordination across sectors. In Cameroon and Kenya, agricultural and environmental institutions often operate in parallel rather than collaboratively, with cross-sectoral coordination occurring mostly in response to crises such as deforestation or encroachment. Colombia shows a more conceptual fragmentation, where dominant policy narratives remain anchored in colonial-modernity imaginaries that separate humans from nature, resulting in governance approaches that marginalize Indigenous relational worldviews. In all cases, coordination gaps undermine the potential for integrated land-use planning, ecosystem-based management, and climate-resilient agricultural strategies.

A fourth shared challenge is the limited incorporation of community knowledge, participation, and benefit-sharing mechanisms. While Kenya has initiated community forest associations and conservancies, these mechanisms remain unevenly operationalized and underfunded. Cameroon's stakeholder interviews highlight limited awareness of policy frameworks among rural populations, weak enforcement capacities, and a perception of biodiversity governance as regulatory rather than supportive. Colombia's policies similarly underrepresent Indigenous ontologies and local histories of cohabitation with nature, leading to governance approaches that risk exclusion and conflict. Across contexts, the insufficient integration of communities into decision-making processes constrains both legitimacy and effectiveness.

Despite these common constraints, important divergences emerge. Kenya's recent policy updates and large-scale initiatives, such as the National Tree Planting Initiative, indicate growing momentum for restoration-oriented programs, albeit still vulnerable to changing political priorities. Cameroon's trajectory shows a notable evolution toward more holistic frameworks in recent national strategies, accompanied by emerging support among grassroots actors for agroecology and nature-based solutions. Colombia's critique-oriented literature and analytical frameworks reveal deeper structural tensions rooted in colonial epistemologies, suggesting that its pathway to transformation may require more fundamental shifts in national imaginaries and governance logics.

Overall, the combined analysis underscores that progress toward integrated biodiversity–agriculture governance remains partial and uneven. The countries have embraced sustainability rhetorically and, in some cases, institutionally, but their development pathways continue to prioritize short-term agricultural productivity over long-term ecological resilience. Bridging this gap will require sustained increases in biodiversity financing, stronger cross-sectoral coordination, and genuine incorporation of Indigenous and local knowledge systems. Additionally, shifting policy imaginaries from control-oriented to relational and care-oriented frameworks is essential for achieving deeper transformation.

Collectively, the findings highlight the need for a paradigm shift that positions biodiversity not as a constraint to development, but as ecological infrastructure essential to agricultural viability, climate adaptation, and social well-being. Such a reframing would enable the three countries to align their development trajectories with global sustainability commitments while addressing the local socioecological realities that shape the human–nature relationship.

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6. Annexes

Annex 1 Nature Futures Framework

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
National Policy for the Integral Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services	2012	A state policy designed to promote the Integrated Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services, aimed at maintaining and enhancing the resilience of socio-ecological systems at national, regional, local, and transboundary levels. It takes into account changing scenarios and fosters joint, coordinated, and collaborative action between the state, the productive sector, and civil society. This policy provides a strategic framework for all environmental management instruments (policies, regulations, plans, programs, and projects), whether existing or in development, to conserve biodiversity across its various levels of organization. Purpose: To ensure the conservation of biodiversity and its ecosystem services, along with the fair and equitable distribution of the benefits derived from them, in order to contribute to the improvement of the quality of life for the Colombian population.		It acknowledges the strategic importance of biodiversity as the primary source, foundation, and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that support the country's development, underpin its competitiveness, and are fundamental to the well-being of Colombian society.	
				It aims to guide the management of biodiversity and its ecosystem services in order to conserve it, address human-induced environmental change, and maintain the resilience of socio-ecological systems, ultimately contributing to the improvement of Colombians' well-being and quality of life.	
				Biodiversity as the foundation of ecosystem services and human well-being	
				Ecosystem services have been recognized as the bridge connecting biodiversity and humanity. This means that efforts historically made to conserve biodiversity are not separate from development; on the contrary, they have significantly contributed to the provision of ecosystem services, which directly and indirectly support all human activities related to production, extraction, settlement, and consumption, as well as the overall well-being of our societies.	
				A framework for action that enables a balance between the diverse societal interests regarding biodiversity and the maintenance of the ecosystem services it provides, which are essential for human well-being.	
				The notion of <i>biodiversity as an asset managed exclusively by the environmental sector</i> and solely under the jurisdiction of the natural sciences is left behind. Instead, a new approach is adopted that <i>promotes shared social and sectoral responsibility</i> , encouraging public participation and recognizing biodiversity and its ecosystem services as a public good. This shift also incorporates biodiversity-related aspects into short-, medium-, and long-term planning to sustainably increase national productivity and competitiveness, while protecting and preserving the country's natural and cultural wealth.	
					[Biodiversity] has been the foundation and contextual framework within which different cultures have developed, giving rise to diverse cultural expressions throughout the national territory. This close relationship, manifested at various scales, is understood as the interdependent connection between ecological systems and social systems, where biodiversity shapes culture, and culture, in turn,

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
					transforms and structures the spatial arrangement of biodiversity. Recognizing this interdependent relationship in every action means understanding and analyzing any territory as a socio-ecosystem, acknowledging that human beings and their culture are integral components of biodiversity ⁴ .
				The relationship between ecological and social systems is established through the continuous provision of ecosystem services—such as provisioning, regulation, cultural, and supporting services—that the ecological system offers at various scales. These services are essential for maintaining human well-being.	
				Conservation should be understood and managed as an emerging property, arising from the balance between preservation actions, sustainable use, knowledge generation, and biodiversity restoration. This approach ensures the maintenance or enhancement of the resilience of socio-ecological systems, thereby sustaining the ecosystem services that are fundamental for human well-being.	
				All actions taken to ensure the conservation of biodiversity must be contextualized within the framework of an environmental management process for the territory. In this context, biodiversity should be recognized as the principal structuring element of territorial planning processes, serving as the source and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that are crucial for the development and sustainability of human activities related to production, extraction, settlement, and consumption.	
				The supply of ecosystem services in adequate quantity and quality is ensured through the integrated management of the territory (a heterogeneous mosaic of productive systems and natural ecosystems).	
				Biodiversity is conceived as a public good (Kelly and Muers, 2003), representing a space for interaction between the state and citizens (both urban and rural). This approach aims to strengthen their relationships and enhance responsiveness, legal security, social responsibility, and the direct and indirect benefits derived from conservation efforts. In doing so, it contributes effectively to achieving objectives such as reducing inequality, alleviating poverty, strengthening democratic states, and fostering active citizenship, moving beyond the outdated notion of biodiversity as solely the responsibility of public sector entities.	

⁴ Combination of nature as culture and nature as nature values

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
				Biodiversity and ecosystem services conservation actions <i>should not be undertaken solely by the environmental sector</i> , but also by productive sectors. Recognizing the role that society as a whole, and each productive sector in particular, plays in achieving responsible territorial management that enables the conservation of biodiversity at national, regional, and local levels is crucial for ensuring the sustainability of key economic activities, such as agriculture and extractive industries. Additionally, maintaining essential ecosystem services is fundamental for the well-being of society as a whole.	
				In the country, there is still a noticeable perception among individuals and sectors that view biodiversity as an obstacle to development or as a "luxury" to be addressed only when the nation's economic growth allows it. This outlook overlooks the fact that biodiversity is the fundamental basis for productive and extractive activities, as it provides essential ecosystem services. Strategies for recognizing and promoting biodiversity within productive and consumer sectors continue to rely primarily on ethical and/or charismatic considerations, rather than on functional and strategic quantitative and qualitative arguments that highlight its contribution to the country's economic and social well-being.	
					It is crucial to move towards integrating the concepts of biodiversity (the environmental aspect) and territorial planning, so that territories are understood as adaptive, resilient, and complex socio-ecosystems with their own structure and functioning. These systems provide ecosystem services and shape the cultural context(s) that develop within them.
				Biodiversity conservation can be understood and managed as the foundation of territorial planning in the country, ensuring the resilience of socio-ecological systems and the continued supply of essential ecosystem services for human well-being. At the same time, this approach reduces socio-ecological vulnerability to risks associated with environmental change.	
			Life is the ultimate value. The survival of life on the planet depends on the protection of both the tangible and intangible components of biodiversity, as well as an understanding of its dynamic nature.		
				The quality of life of the population is reciprocally and inseparably linked to the conservation of biodiversity and its ecosystem services.	
				Biodiversity is the source, foundation, and guarantee of the supply of ecosystem services, which are essential for the sustainable development of the country, for its adaptation to global environmental changes, and for the well-being of Colombian society.	

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
				Biological diversity is closely linked to ethnic and cultural diversity. Recognizing these connections and respecting cultural differences are essential in designing local conservation strategies. These strategies must be integrated with development and land-use policies to ensure sustainable use.	
				Biodiversity is the foundation of the country's natural and economic wealth, and one of its main comparative advantages over other nations worldwide.	
National Development Plan 2010-2014 [Aims] "to make a leap in social progress, fostering regional economic dynamism that enables sustainable development and consistent growth, with more formal employment, reduced poverty, and, ultimately, greater prosperity for the entire population." [Embraces] "a strategy for sustained growth based on a more competitive, productive, and innovative economy, with dynamic sectors that propel growth forward."	2010	Agricultural policy		"Ownership of lands that were originally allocated as public vacant lands or acquired through comprehensive land subsidies, even if this results in consolidated properties with areas exceeding the limits set for Family Agricultural Units (UAF) by INCODER, is permitted as long as the properties in question are part of an agricultural or forestry development project that justifies the operation.	
				Authorization for the utilization of public vacant lands	
				National Commercial Reforestation Program aimed at harnessing the country's forestry potential and expanding productive capacity, contributing to the rehabilitation of soils suitable for reforestation, including river basins and their connected areas	
				In pursuit of its social purpose, Banco Agrario de Colombia S.A. (Banagrario) may conduct all operations authorized for banking credit institutions, as well as engage in transactions involving commodity price derivatives to mitigate credit, market, or liquidity risks	
National Development Plan 2014-2018 "its aim is to build a peaceful, equitable, and educated Colombia, [...] guided by a long-term planning vision aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals".	2014	Mining and energy policy		If the granting of a water concession for the use of water resources in the operation of power generation plants is deemed viable, it will be granted for a minimum period of twenty years and up to fifty years.	
		Agricultural policy		To establish reserves on vacant lands, or lands that may later acquire this status, in order to implement a special regime of occupation, use, and allocation regulated by the National Government. This will allow the beneficiary to have land as an asset to initiate income-generating activities.	
				The special regime for occupation, utilization, and allocation will also apply to vacant lands that become eligible for allocation as a result of the release of forest reserve areas under Law 2 of 1959, provided they have agricultural and/or forestry production potential.	

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
				a deforestation control initiative that will include an action plan aimed at preventing the loss of natural forests by 2030. This policy will contain provisions to meaningfully engage sectors driving deforestation, including production chains that utilize forests and forest-based products.	
			They may partially or fully restrict the development of high-impact agricultural, mining, and hydrocarbon exploration and exploitation activities, based on technical, economic, social, and environmental studies, in accordance with the guidelines established by the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development		
			In areas designated as páramos, agricultural activities, exploration or exploitation of non-renewable natural resources, and the construction of hydrocarbon refineries are not permitted.		
				Environmental authorities, in coordination with and supported by local entities, will advance the necessary co-financing plans to acquire areas or strategic ecosystems for the conservation, preservation, and restoration of natural resources. Alternatively, they will implement payment for environmental services schemes or other economic incentives for conservation, in accordance with regulations issued by the National Government.	
					The National Government must establish an intersectoral coordination body to ensure a sustainable development model that promotes and guarantees participatory territorial agreements for human and environmentally sustainable development. This body will generate sectoral agendas aimed at strengthening competitive and sustainable value chains, allowing for the creation of mechanisms and alternatives for the appropriate and responsible use of the environment and natural resources, as well as protecting biodiversity and the traditional knowledge of Indigenous communities in the Amazon.
National Development Plan 2018-2022 "Its objective is to lay the foundations of legality, entrepreneurship, and equity to achieve equal opportunities for all Colombians, in alignment with the [...] Sustainable Development	2018				Agreements with vulnerable rural populations who inhabit, occupy, or engage in traditional practices associated with the rural economy in protected areas, deriving their livelihood from these practices, will be recognized by the entities that enter into agreements. This recognition will acknowledge their artisanal and traditional productive relationship within the protected area, aiming to help address conflicts related to use, occupation, and tenure
			To specify actions to halt deforestation and implement new reforestation and afforestation strategies. These public policies must be developed and executed within the framework of legality, entrepreneurship, and equity.		

Policy	Year	Description	"Nature for nature," which prioritizes nature's intrinsic value and the preservation of its functions	"Nature for society," which emphasizes nature's benefits for human use	"Nature as culture," where humans are seen as an integral part of nature and its processes
Goals 2030"				The conservation of the forests in the Amazon region is essential, as this area contains the largest expanse of forests in the country, making it a center for sustainable economic and environmental development due to the biodiversity it harbors.	
				Preservation, restoration, sustainable use, and income generation from the páramos	

Annex 2 Life Frames Framework

Policy	Year	Policy description	'living from' frame centers on nature's capacity to provide tangible resources that support livelihoods.	The 'living in' frame recognizes nature as an essential part of people's daily lives, identities, and cultural practices.	'living with' frame acknowledges the importance of life-supporting ecological systems and moral consideration for other-than-human beings.	'living as' frame expresses a profound sense of oneness, kinship, and interdependence with nature.
National Policy for the Integral Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services	2012	A state policy designed to promote the Integrated Management of Biodiversity and its Ecosystem Services, aimed at maintaining and enhancing the resilience of socio-ecological systems at national, regional, local, and transboundary levels. It takes into account changing scenarios and fosters joint, coordinated, and collaborative action between the state, the productive sector, and civil society. This policy provides a strategic framework for all environmental management instruments (policies, regulations, plans, programs, and projects), whether existing or in development, to conserve biodiversity across its various levels of organization. Purpose: To ensure the conservation of biodiversity and its ecosystem services, along with the fair and equitable distribution of the benefits derived from them, in order to contribute to the improvement of the quality of life for the Colombian population.	It acknowledges the strategic importance of biodiversity as the primary source, foundation, and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that support the country's development, underpin its competitiveness, and are fundamental to the well-being of Colombian society.			
			It aims to guide the management of biodiversity and its ecosystem services in order to conserve it, address human-induced environmental change, and maintain the resilience of socio-ecological systems, ultimately contributing to the improvement of Colombians' well-being and quality of life.			
			A framework for action that enables a balance between the diverse societal interests regarding biodiversity and the maintenance of the ecosystem services it provides, which are essential for human well-being.			
			The notion of biodiversity as an asset managed exclusively by the environmental sector and solely under the jurisdiction of the natural sciences is left behind. Instead, a new approach is adopted that promotes shared social and sectoral responsibility, encouraging public participation and recognizing biodiversity and its ecosystem services as a public good. This shift also incorporates biodiversity-related aspects into short-, medium-, and long-term planning to sustainably increase national productivity and competitiveness, while protecting and preserving the country's natural and cultural wealth.			

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				[Biodiversity] has been the foundation and contextual framework within which different cultures have developed, giving rise to diverse cultural expressions throughout the national territory. This close relationship, manifested at various scales, is understood as the interdependent connection between ecological systems and social systems, where biodiversity shapes culture, and culture, in turn, transforms and structures the spatial arrangement of biodiversity. Recognizing this interdependent relationship in every action means understanding and analyzing any territory as a socio-ecosystem, acknowledging that human beings and their culture are integral components of biodiversity.		
				The relationship between ecological and social systems is established through the continuous provision of ecosystem services—such as provisioning, regulation, cultural, and supporting services—that the ecological system offers at various scales. These services are essential for maintaining human well-being.		
			Conservation should be understood and managed as an emerging property, arising from the balance between preservation actions, sustainable use, knowledge generation, and biodiversity restoration. This approach ensures the maintenance or enhancement of the resilience of socio-ecological systems, thereby sustaining the ecosystem services that are fundamental for human well-being.			
			biodiversity should be recognized as the principal structuring element of territorial planning processes, serving as the source and guarantor of essential ecosystem services that are crucial for the development			

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			and sustainability of human activities related to production, extraction, settlement, and consumption.			
			The supply of ecosystem services in adequate quantity and quality is ensured through the integrated management of the territory (a heterogeneous mosaic of productive systems and natural ecosystems).			
				Biodiversity is conceived as a public good (Kelly and Muers, 2003), representing a space for interaction between the state and citizens (both urban and rural). This approach aims to strengthen their relationships and enhance responsiveness, legal security, social responsibility, and the direct and indirect benefits derived from conservation efforts. In doing so, it contributes effectively to achieving objectives such as reducing inequality, alleviating poverty, strengthening democratic states, and fostering active citizenship, moving beyond the outdated notion of biodiversity as solely the responsibility of public sector entities.		
			Recognizing the role that society as a whole, and each productive sector in particular, plays in achieving responsible territorial management that enables the conservation of biodiversity at national, regional, and local levels is crucial for ensuring the sustainability of key economic activities, such as agriculture and extractive industries. Additionally, maintaining essential ecosystem services is fundamental for the well-being of society as a whole.			

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			This outlook overlooks the fact that biodiversity is the fundamental basis for productive and extractive activities, as it provides essential ecosystem services. Strategies for recognizing and promoting biodiversity within productive and consumer sectors continue to rely primarily on ethical and/or charismatic considerations, rather than on functional and strategic quantitative and qualitative arguments that highlight its contribution to the country's economic and social well-being.			
				Territories are understood as adaptive, resilient, and complex socio-ecosystems with their own structure and functioning. These systems provide ecosystem services and shape the cultural context(s) that develop within them.		
				Biodiversity conservation can be understood and managed as the foundation of territorial planning in the country, ensuring the resilience of socio-ecological systems and the continued supply of essential ecosystem services for human well-being. At the same time, this approach reduces socio-ecological vulnerability to risks associated with environmental change.		
					Life is the ultimate value. The survival of life on the planet depends on the protection of both the tangible and intangible components of biodiversity, as well as an understanding of its dynamic nature.	
			The quality of life of the population is reciprocally and inseparably linked to the conservation of biodiversity and its ecosystem services.			
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			development of the country, for its adaptation to global environmental changes, and for the well-being of Colombian society.			
				Biological diversity is closely linked to ethnic and cultural diversity. Recognizing these connections and respecting cultural differences are essential in designing local conservation strategies. These strategies must be integrated with development and land-use policies to ensure sustainable use.		
			Biodiversity is the foundation of the country's natural and economic wealth, and one of its main comparative advantages over other nations worldwide.			
National Development Plan 2010-2014	2010	[Aims] "to make a leap in social progress, fostering regional economic dynamism that enables sustainable development and consistent growth, with more formal employment, reduced poverty, and, ultimately, greater prosperity for the entire population." [Embraces] "a strategy for sustained growth based on a more competitive, productive, and innovative economy, with dynamic sectors that propel growth forward."	Ownership of lands that were originally allocated as public vacant lands or acquired through comprehensive land subsidies, even if this results in consolidated properties with areas exceeding the limits set for Family Agricultural Units (UAF) by INCODER, is permitted as long as the properties in question are part of an agricultural or forestry development project that justifies the operation.			
			National Commercial Reforestation Program aimed at harnessing the country's forestry potential and expanding productive capacity, contributing to the rehabilitation of soils suitable for reforestation, including river basins and their connected areas			
National Development Plan 2014-2018	2014	"Its aim is to build a peaceful, equitable, and educated Colombia, [...] guided by a long-term planning vision aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals".	If the granting of a water concession for the use of water resources in the operation of power generation plants is deemed viable, it will be granted for a minimum period of twenty years and up to fifty years.			
			To establish reserves on vacant lands, or lands that may later acquire this status, in order to implement a special regime of occupation, use, and			

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			allocation regulated by the National Government. This will allow the beneficiary to have land as an asset to initiate income-generating activities.			
			The special regime for occupation, utilization, and allocation will also apply to vacant lands that become eligible for allocation as a result of the release of forest reserve areas under Law 2 of 1959, provided they have agricultural and/or forestry production potential.			
					In areas designated as páramos, agricultural activities, exploration or exploitation of non-renewable natural resources, and the construction of hydrocarbon refineries are not permitted.	
National Development Plan 2018-2022	2018	"Its objective is to lay the foundations of legality, entrepreneurship, and equity to achieve equal opportunities for all Colombians, in alignment with the [...] Sustainable Development Goals 2030"		Agreements with vulnerable rural populations who inhabit, occupy, or engage in traditional practices associated with the rural economy in protected areas, deriving their livelihood from these practices, will be recognized by the entities that enter into agreements. This recognition will acknowledge their artisanal and traditional productive relationship within the protected area, aiming to help address conflicts related to use, occupation, and tenure		
				The conservation of the forests in the Amazon region is essential, as this area contains the largest expanse of forests in the country, making it a center for sustainable economic and environmental development due to the biodiversity it harbors.		
				Preservation, restoration, sustainable use, and income generation from the páramos		